

RURITAGE

Heritage for Rural Regeneration

D2.1 – RURITAGE methodology for Community- based Heritage Management and Planning (CHMP)

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Background information

Table 1: technical Information

Project Full title	Rural regeneration through systemic heritage-led strategies	
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Table 2: Revision History

D	Deliverable
WP	Work Package
M	Month
RHH	Rural Heritage Hub
RM	Role Model
R	Replicator
SIA	Systemic Innovation Area
CNH	Cultural and Natural Heritage
CHMP	Methodology for Community based Heritage Management and Planning
PIS	Project Information Sheet
ICF	Data protection Informed Consent Form

Executive Summary

WP2 aims to foster social innovation potential and ensure knowledge transfer and mutual learning between RMs and Rs and other project partners. One of the tasks of this WP (T2.1) relates to the preparation of the basis for **participatory, multi-stakeholder and trans-disciplinary process through the development of the RURITAGE Methodology for Community based Heritage Management and Planning – CHMP (D2.1)** to be implemented in the course of WP3 ‘Co-development and co-implementing heritage-led rural regeneration plans in Replicators’. This methodology aims to provide guidance for the undertaking of dedicated activities organized within the Rural Heritage Hubs in Role Models and Replicators to develop and enhance heritage-led regeneration strategy.

The innovation potential of this deliverable relies on the fact that co-development and co-implementation process are commonly implemented in urban areas, while **these processes are quite uncommon in rural areas**. The ambition of this Methodology for Community based Heritage Management and Planning -CHMP- is indeed to provide not just project partners, but all potentially interested rural areas, with a theoretical background and an operative programme to co- develop heritage-led regeneration strategies in rural areas. The role of the Rural Heritage Hub as a central innovation space assumes in this context a great importance representing the intersection of social, cultural and technological innovation of rural areas.

Moreover, based on the RURITAGE paradigm of the 6 Systemic Innovation Areas (SIAs) -Migration, Local food production, integrated landscape management, art and festival, pilgrimage and resilience- activities specific to each SIA and differentiated between Rs and RMs and tailored co-design approaches and methods are proposed in the CHMP. A calendar and description with planned activities for all the Rs and RMs are also included. In addition, the methodology provides information on the concepts of participatory planning, co-creation and stakeholders’ engagement and practical guidance relating Hub activities’ dissemination, potential risks and corrective measures and related ethics and data protection issues.

The present deliverable is structured in different sections, so that RMs and Rs and any other interested parties, can go through the document and consult their preferred information easily:

1. **Section 1:** theoretical and methodological approach to the participatory process.
2. **Section 2:** approach for activating, managing and monitoring the Hubs which shall be conceived as multifunctional spaces. This is a more operational section tackling **three phases**:
 - Phase 1 - Setting the Hubs
 - Phase 2 - Activities to be implemented in the Hubs
 - Phase 3 - Monitoring the Hubs
3. **Section 3:** useful material and tools for the Hubs (Digital Heritage Hub, Dissemination and communication, Potential risks and solutions, Ethics and data protection).

The present methodology shall not be considered as a standalone document, but it has been drafted taking into account all the interrelations with other deliverables and tasks, especially those coming from **WP1, WP3, WP5, WP7 and WP2** itself. In this sense, it shall be underlined that RMs and Rs will, of course, implement their activities within their own local Rural Heritage Hub; however, this process will not only remain at local level, but it will be fed by the results of other WPs and the collaboration and mutual learning happening between RMs and Rs.

Figure 1 – RHH local activities’ timeline

The timeline above shows how the Hubs’ activities’ implementation will run in parallel with the tasks of other WPs and with the mutual learning process among Rs and RMs. For Rs the mentoring and capacity building process with RMs, that will happen throughout WP2, will be fundamental for the definition of their heritage-led regeneration plans. Moreover, much of the ideas and the solutions that will be discussed into the co-development phase of the Rs will be based on the outcomes of WP1 (lessons learnt, ATLAS and best practices repository). Last, all the digital tools developed through WP5 will be of course made available to project partners at the end of the first year of the project.

Section 1

Theoretical and methodological approach to the participatory process into the Rural Heritage Hub

1. Co-creation concept and participatory planning processes

Co-creation is a form of collaborative creativity that was initiated by firms first to enable innovation with, rather than simply for their customers. The user-centred design approach has been primarily a US-driven phenomenon. In Europe, much of the activity in participatory design has been going on in the Northern countries (in particular Norway, Sweden and Denmark), where the Collective Resource Approach was established to increase the value of industrial production by engaging workers in the development of new systems for the workplace.

Within this framework, the notions of co-creation, co-design and co-production have been growing. **Co-creation refers to any act of collective creativity which means that creativity is shared by two or more people.** These new types of processes encourage new behaviours, roles and relationships. Citizens are no longer passive, but they participate as active members of the process providing inputs and they become a very valuable information source because of their final user perspective.

The concept of co-creation had an evolution and has been transferred from the business sector to public-private collaboration, as in the case of Living Labs. Living Labs are an emerging Public Private Partnership (PPP) concept in which firms, public authorities and citizens work together to create, validate and test new services, businesses, markets and technologies in real-life contexts (Niitamo, Kulkki, Eriksson, Hribernik, 2006), such as cities, city regions, rural areas and collaborative virtual networks between public and private players. The public is considered co-producers of service, policy or innovation and can help the government in solving problems faster and accurately by harnessing a collaborative network of citizen experts (Albury, 2005; Arganoff, 2007).

In this line, the past decade has witnessed shifts in the rhetoric of rural development leading to reversals from top-down to bottom-up, from centralized standardization to local diversity, and from blueprint to learning process. In these changes, a part has been played by two closely related families of approaches and of methods, often referred to as **rapid rural appraisal (RRA)** which developed and spread especially in the 1980s and its further evolution into **participatory rural appraisal (PRA)** which has developed and spread fast in the 1990s. Participatory rural appraisal methods are increasingly taken up by public sector organizations as well as NGOs among whom they have been pioneered (Chambers, 1994). PRA describes a growing family of approaches and methods to enable local people to share, enhance and analyze their knowledge of life and conditions, to plan and to act. PRA has sources in activist participatory research, agroecosystem analysis, applied anthropology, field research on farming systems, and rapid rural appraisal – RRA). In RRA information is more elicited and extracted by outsiders; in PRA it is more shared and owned by local people. In particular, PRAs involve ‘public’ social events which construct ‘local knowledge’ in ways that are strongly influenced by existing social relationships (Mosse, 1994). PRA applications include natural resources management, agriculture, poverty and social programs, and health and food security (Chambers, 1992).

Community participation, being one of the strong features of decentralized planning, is important to achieve socio-economic uplift. Active involvement of the community helps in preparation and execution of effective development action plans by making assessment of the felt needs and

constraints of the people easier. Participation of community members in the development planning process also helps in mobilizing resources for effective plan implementation.

Likewise, the **ambition of RURITAGE is to foster participatory management, responsibility and ownership of CNH in RMs and Rs through the establishment of Rural Heritage Hubs conceived as multifunctional spaces** meaning that they are not only social spaces, but also physical spots where to meet and exchange ideas, practices and experiences. While it is becoming increasingly common to set up living labs, innovation hubs, and co-creation processes within urban areas, this approach is not equally developed in rural areas. The transposition of this approach to rural areas will represent a major achievement in this field thanks to RURITAGE activities. Through the collective community-management in place within the Hubs, RURITAGE will gather stakeholders and local communities in a new form of collaboration, engaging them in a participatory and community-based heritage management and planning. This innovative approach includes employing serious games that, as it has been demonstrated, help participants understand the real world complexity, foster creativity, and support consensus building, in effect leading to increased commitment to action.

2. Stakeholder and participatory approaches

In the simplest terms stakeholders can be defined as individuals or groups who affect or are affected by a policy. Stakeholder participation can thus be defined as a **process where individuals, groups and organisations are invited and choose to take an active role in making decisions that affect them** (Wandersman, 1981; Wilcox, 2003; Rowe et al., 2004). Stakeholder participation differs thus from broader public participation, since stakeholders are only those who can affect or be affected by a decision.

Stakeholder participation in policy decision-making have several benefits. First of all, quality and durability of decisions is greater (e.g. Fischer, 2000; Beierle, 2002; Reed et al., 2008). Information from stakeholders brought into the deliberation contributes to avoid unintended consequences of decisions, such as environmental ones, and more adherence of those to existing contexts. Secondly, social consensus is more easily reached. Stakeholders engagement increases public understanding of the issues and consequences of different choices and reveals both conflicts and agreements among different stakeholder groups. At the same time, open and inclusive stakeholder engagement, including representatives of different viewpoints, can sometimes resolve differences and build trust in the policy making process and therefore help secure public acceptance of decisions (e.g., Kleivink, et al, 2012). Finally, the process of decision-making and final decisions becomes more transparent and legitimate.

Stakeholders can thus be **any type of organisations and individuals which can affect or be affected by a policy**. In stakeholder engagement processes, organisations are represented by one or more individuals and can include: public authorities, research organisations, formal and non-formal education establishments, companies and social enterprises, business support organizations and business associations, no-profit organisations, including associations, foundations, NGOs, and civil society organisations. Physical persons can be represented by either an organisation or not informal groups (groups of families, of neighbours, etc, or can be consulted and engaged individually.

Different typologies of stakeholders' participation exist: the diversity lies mainly in the different degree of involvement and in the way knowledge flows from and among decision-makers, researchers and stakeholders. Deliverable 3.1 - Guidelines for stakeholders' identification and engagement within the RHHs has identified a series of stakeholder groups of interest for the RURITAGE project's purposes:

1. Policy: to change policy frameworks and goals. This implies regional and local governments.
2. Research: to help inform research. Examples of stakeholders are indeed universities, research centres.
3. Industry / services / investors: to support the creation of new business models and sources of funding. Examples from these categories are the representatives of key value chains, public and private investors, and key service providers in rural areas.
4. Public: to inform and empower communities. Examples are schools, civil society organisations, Local Action Groups, individual citizens.

A participatory approach is thus an approach in which everyone who has a stake in the intervention has a voice, either in person or by representation, and the right to contribute to a decision-making process. In this sense, a participatory approach does not include simple communication where stakeholders receive an information or provide information and knowledge to well-defined questions.

For a decision-making process to be participatory, stakeholders need to be consulted early in the process and with an open and iterative approach, which allows them to provide inputs and suggestions for the decisions to be taken and feedback on reformulation of decisions by policy-makers. The table below, taken from FAO, describes well the differences among typologies of participation.

Passive Participation	People participate by being told what is going to happen or has already happened. It is a unilateral announcement by an administration or project management without any listening to people's responses.
Participation in information giving	The information being shared belongs only to external professionals. People participate by answering questions posed by extractive researchers using questionnaire surveys or such similar approaches. People do not have the opportunity to influence proceedings, as the findings of the research are neither shared nor checked for accuracy.
Participation by consultation	People participate by being consulted, and external agents listen to views. These external agents define both problems and solutions, and may modify these in the light of people's responses. Such a consultative process does not concede any share in decision making, and professionals are under no obligation to take on board people's views.

Functional participation	People participate by forming groups to meet predetermined objectives related to the project, which can involve the development or promotion of externally initiated social organisation. Such involvement tends not to be at early stages of project cycles or planning, but rather after major decisions have already been made. These institutions tend to be dependent on external initiators and facilitators, but may become self-dependent.
Interactive participation	People participate in joint analysis, which leads to action plans and the formation of new local institutions or the strengthening of existing ones. It tends to involve interdisciplinary methodologies that seek multiple objectives and make use of systematic and structured learning processes. These groups take control/ownership over local decisions, and so people have a stake in maintaining structures or practices.

To face the complexity of societal challenges policy making needs to be knowledge-based. Traditionally, researchers were considered the knowledge holders and the terms ‘knowledge transfer’ and ‘knowledge brokerage’ have been increasingly used to describe the process of generating knowledge based on user needs, disseminating it, building capacity for its uptake by decision-makers, and finally tracking its application in specific contexts. The concept of Knowledge Brokerage is associated with this process and it is analysed in the following section.

3. Knowledge brokerage and information gathering

Knowledge Brokerage is not a new concept. The meaning of **Knowledge Brokerage** in literature is generally understood as an **intermediary activity that takes place between and within the spheres of science, policy and civil society in order to bridge the research-to-practice gap** (e.g. Roxborough et al. 2007) or the knowledge-to-action gap (e.g. Strauss et al. 2009) or more generally to manage the boundaries between science, policy and practice (e.g. Michaels 2009) and to link the producers and users of research (Ward et al. 2010).

Such intermediary activities are designed to build relationships and foster effective knowledge exchange. The purpose of Knowledge Brokerage activities is often related to support the identification, access, assessment, interpretation and the use of research findings for evidence-based policy making, and the uptake in practice, which addresses an interaction with relevant stakeholder groups or the public in general.

3.1. Different levels of Knowledge Brokerage

Knowledge Brokerage activities may be located at **different levels** – referring to the individual level, a group or an organisation (Currie et al. 2010):

a) Individual level: knowledge brokerage is done by a person, who overtakes the role of a boundary spanner between the different realms of research and policy and/or practice by translating, transferring, and exchanging knowledge (e.g. consultants, advisors).

b) Group level: At the group level of brokering social capital represents a means through which knowledge is exchanged. The development of social capital within a network or community requires that actors are connected to each other (structural dimension), understand each other's perspectives (cognitive dimension) and trust each other (relational dimension). Through situated interactions, actors engaged in the Knowledge Brokerage activities build up trust and understanding that encourage them to exchange knowledge.

c) At the organisational level of brokering, boundary spanning institutions/organisations may develop: they either could be independent or affiliated to one of the realm (e.g. universities' knowledge transfer departments, liaising departments at ministries, etc.). Knowledge brokers at the organisational level mediate divergent interests by focusing on organisational mechanisms and processes that enable collaboration, and in so doing, they selectively broker knowledge to induce collective action and enhance co-operation amongst actors engaged (Currie et al. 2010).

As described by Currie et al. 2010, much of the literature on Knowledge Brokerage focuses upon the individual level. However, analysis at the individual level applies to the cases of group and organisational level Knowledge Brokerage.

3.2 Knowledge Brokerage strategies

Knowledge Brokerage includes **diverse strategies**. These strategies vary in relation to the actors engaged (different types of researchers, policy makers, civil society or other actors), the type of knowledge being shared, and the specific context. Michaels (2009) reviewed Knowledge Brokerage strategies in the context of policy decision making; thereby she identified the following six that might be employed in responding to different types of policy problems or policy settings:

- **Inform:** The intent of informing is to disseminate content. In this case, the recipient understands the significance of what is being presented and may well accept the information on face value.
- **Consult:** This process involves someone who is accountable for a problem looking for counselling, seeks someone regarded as having potentially valuable insights, if not solutions, into the problem at hand.
- **Matchmake:** Matchmaking brings together individuals who can contribute to an envisaged action (e.g. policy decision making). Through brokerage the actors are brought together; the broker needs to identify what expertise is needed, and who can provide it in order to connect these people.
- **Engage:** Engaging as a form of brokering involves the party who is responsible for addressing the problem establishing and implementing a process of involving others with salient expertise.

- **Collaborate:** Collaborating involves all participants in jointly framing the process of how they interact with each other, and to negotiate how to scope the problem to be addressed.
- **Build capacity:** Capacity building refers to the ability of people and institutions to do what is required of them'. To build capacity in the scope of Knowledge Brokerage parties jointly frame process of interaction and negotiate substance with intent of addressing multiple dimensions of a problem while considering what can be learned from doing so.
- While informing, consulting and matchmaking often require a low level of involvement, engaging, collaborating and capacity building need higher levels of engagement and personal interaction in order to be effective.

3.3 Knowledge Brokerage actions

Knowledge brokerage **actions** need to take into account different perspectives and issues concerning the relation between participants in the co-creation and the way the information and knowledge flows among participants. The list below describes the main issues to be taken into consideration while designing knowledge brokerage actions:

- **Relationships of trust and confidence:** the quality of Knowledge Brokerage depends on the type and quality of relationships between engaged actors; key factors in successful Knowledge Brokerage and collaboration are relationships of trust and confidence; frequent interaction that reinforces high trust relationships represent a prerequisite for effective knowledge brokering or driving research into practice.
- **Customised activities:** Knowledge Brokerage activities which are customised to specific contexts are more likely to support the uptake of evidence into policy decisions and practice.
- **Non-linear process:** One-directional knowledge transfer from the producers to the users of research is not very likely to be beneficial for research utilisation in evidence informed policy and practice (Armstrong et al. 2006).
- **Combining activities:** A combination of different activities, e.g. tailored messages and interactive activities engaging researchers and policy makers to discuss research findings and their potential implications for practice positively influences the use of research evidence. A process that reaches potential users on multiple levels is considered being very effective in achieving evidence-informed decision making.
- **Transfer of tailored information:** Decision-makers prefer to receive research evidence in form of systematic reviews based on the culmination of many studies versus single studies.
- **Tailored activities:** Knowledge brokerage activities should be tailored to suit all actors engaged. Techniques to help facilitate knowledge exchange and transfer among

stakeholders should explicitly recognise the diversity of types of knowledge represented by different stakeholders.

- **Communication:** Appropriate communication styles and tools should be chosen according to the different types of stakeholders/actors engaged. The shared language should correspond to different types of knowledge involved.
- **Language barriers:** For activities engaging actors from different language areas, it is important to implement measures (e.g. use of specific tools, provision of translation services, language support, conscious facilitation) to avoid language barriers. This could be particularly relevant for activities engaging actors of different educational background, but the capability to cope with foreign languages may also differ amongst age groups.
- **Online tools:** Online tools to be used for Knowledge Brokerage activities need to be carefully chosen and designed in line with the actors' capabilities of using such tools. It needs much effort to mobilise people: for example, in the beginning certain actors may be quite reluctant in engaging in online interaction; regular training sessions and technical support is a way to facilitate the use of online tools.
- **Relational issues:** It is helpful to address relational issues between those involved in the Knowledge Brokerage process in order to address differences between the communities.
- **Process flexibility:** In order to enhance strategic thinking and adaptive management process openness, process iteration and flexibility is important. A certain flexibility of the process is also necessary if adjustments according to participants' needs and expectations are requested.

3.4 Knowledge Brokerage skills

Finally, for RURITAGE purposes it is important to note that there is some evidence that personality characteristics of knowledge brokers' influence Knowledge Brokerage activities. A core set of **brokering skills** necessary to carry out effective Knowledge Brokerage has been identified by several authors as summarised by Roxborough et al. (2009):

- **Personal attributes:** Knowledge brokers should be inquisitive, enthusiastic, flexible, inspirational, imaginative, highly credible and keenly interested in learning. They should be skilled analysts, able to see the 'big picture' and be able to readily identify links between ideas and pieces of information.
- **Critical appraisal skills:** Knowledge brokers should be able to appraise evidence to evaluate its quality, importance, and applicability to a particular context. In addition to traditional critical appraisal skills, they should have knowledge of the sector, the broader environment (e.g. policy context), its key players and controversies - and use this to gauge the applicability and adaptability of new evidence to user contexts.

- **Communication skills:** Knowledge brokers should have strong oral and written communication skills and use a variety of methods targeted to the needs of the diverse stakeholders. They should use active listening skills to gain insight into the interests, issues and innovations of their network members.
- **Mediation skills:** To function as effective relationship builders, knowledge brokers should be skilled mediators. They assemble teams and foster collaboration amongst individuals and groups who would not normally work together. They reconcile misunderstandings, facilitate the identification of shared goals, and negotiate mutually beneficial roles for all group members.

3.5 Knowledge brokerage in RURITAGE

RURITAGE Knowledge Brokerage concept refers to a participatory group process during which participants exchange information and ideas to co-develop and co-implement heritage-led rural strategies. Knowledge brokerage activities need also to ensure a long-term engagement of participants in order to reduce to a larger extent participants' leaving and withdrawing from the **Rural Heritage Hub exercise**.

For this reason, knowledge Brokerage in the project will include:

• Development, maintenance, and facilitation of networks linking researchers, decision-makers and civil society
• Support of social interaction and trust to promote a better understanding of different contexts
• Shaping group learning processes
• Synthesizing existing knowledge (from different sources)
• Support of communication processes
• Support for evidence informed decision making
• Guiding citizens and civil society organisations in accessing, appraising, adapting and applying research evidence
• Helping researchers, decision-makers and civil society organisations to define policy priorities
• Assessing context with attention to supports and barriers for knowledge exchange
• Support of capacity building in all the Hubs
• Helping to translate research needs articulated by non-researchers into research

Although participatory planning approaches have been applied to a great number of projects and initiatives around Europe up to date, and it is ever becoming a more common practice, it is still somehow occurring more often in urban cities rather than rural or peripheral areas. RURITAGE intends to bridge this gap and apply this approach in rural areas, using the set-up of Hubs in each RM's and R's as scenarios for change, where a wide range of actors are allowed participate in the decision-making process and contribute actively to this successful shift. Some of the **good practices from other EU-funded projects and other initiatives where participatory planning and co-creation**

approaches have been successful (and still are) are presented in the table below, from which RURITAGE already capitalizes.

Project/initiative	Good practice description
SMARTICIPATE project (H2020 Programme, EU-funded)	<p>The SMARTICIPATE project (2016-2019) aims to integrate bottom-up processes in city planning, using the full potential of citizens by sharing ideas in the co-production of decision making. It transforms interaction between citizens, businesses and public administrations in the management of cities, providing a must-have tool that improves cities' performance, leverages government-citizen relationships, reduces burdens on government via co-production of tasks, and saves money through increased efficiency of processes.</p> <p>As a consequence, citizens get full access to public open data and feedback on their neighborhood-related and citywide ideas for city development. This is achieved in a playful, digital dialogue based on the creation of an open, easily accessible platform. This allows government, NGOs, businesses and citizens to develop their own apps as producers and co-producers. As a result, citizens are empowered to play active roles in the public domain, to develop new tools and to generate new public services.</p> <p>https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/200063_en.html</p>
HERCULES project (FP7 programme, EU-funded)	<p>The HERCULES project (Sustainable futures for Europe's HERitage in CULtural landscapES: Tools for understanding, managing, and protecting landscape functions and values), which run from 2013 until 2016, sought for for the empowerment of public and private actors to protect, manage, and plan for sustainable landscapes of significant cultural, historical, and archaeological value at local, national, and pan-European scales. By applying and developing innovative technologies and tools for assessing and mapping cultural landscapes, the project aimed to (a) synthesise existing knowledge on drivers, patterns, and outcomes of persistence and change in Europe's cultural landscapes; (b) perform targeted case studies to develop in-depth insights on dynamics and values of cultural landscapes; (c) develop a typology of cultural landscapes and scale-up case study insights using observations and landscape modelling; (d) develop visions for re-coupling social and ecological components in cultural landscapes and translate them into policy and management options; and (e) design and implement a community-based Knowledge Hub for Good Landscape Practice and demonstrate it with land users, agencies, SMEs, and citizen associations.</p> <p>https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/110482_en.html</p>
<i>Laboratori di Quartiere</i> (Bologna, IT)	<p>In 2017, <i>Immaginazione Civica</i> launched the initiative <i>Laboratori di Quartiere</i> (Neighbourhood Labs) in collaboration with the reformed</p>

	<p>Districts of Bologna, the University of Bologna and the Municipality. The initiative is inserted in the Urban Innovation Plan of the City of Bologna as an attempt to experiment and manage structured and permanent participatory and collaborative processes in every District of the city. Specifically, it is oriented to the transformation of proximity areas, public space and public buildings.</p> <p>The Urban Innovation Plan, and hence the <i>Laboratori di Quartiere</i>, counts with network of buildings and public areas where citizens and communities can experiment new forms of being together, renovate and strengthen social bonds, contrast social and individual vulnerability in order to enable the social capital of the city.</p> <p>The Laboratories:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Are “spaces” dedicated to the interaction and the construction of relations. ● Activate participatory and co-design processes oriented to the integration of municipal and districts’ policies. ● Are based on peculiar methodologies to guarantee an open, inclusive and fair interaction and citizens’ representation. ● Use open data and new technologies to be accountable and effective. ● Are committed to the engagement of excluded populations: young people, migrant communities, social and economic vulnerable categories. <p>Succeed</p> <p>Every year, Labs will be activated by Bologna’s districts on the basis of the planned investments, citizens’ recommendations, socio-economic priorities.</p> <p>https://eucanet.files.wordpress.com/2017/12/labquartiere_english-presentation_last.pdf</p>
<p><i>Decidim.barcelona</i> platform (Barcelona, ES)</p>	<p><i>Decidim.barcelona</i> is the Barcelona City Council’s web platform for participatory democracy. It serves as a user-friendly, mobile-first, digital infrastructure to build a more democratic city. Thanks to <i>Decidim</i>, all citizens have access to the participation channels and mechanisms that are active in the city.</p> <p>Since its launch on February 1st, 2016, 28.552 people have joined the platform. They have made 12.520 proposals, casted 190.240 votes or supports to proposals, and 9.011 proposals have been turned into public policy so far. Moreover, the site allows citizens to audit the progress in the execution of these proposals, or discuss the reasons for being rejected (when a proposal is finally turned into public policy).</p>

	<p>Strategic city and district planning, the elaboration of new participation regulation, urban projects, the management of municipal infrastructure, citizen initiatives for popular consultation, participatory budgeting or the design of public policies, more broadly, are some of the participatory processes hosted by the platform.</p> <p>There are currently more than 34 institutions and organizations in the world that have installed and use <i>Decidim</i>: ranging from municipalities such as Helsinki or Pamplona, to regional governments like the Junta de Castilla la Mancha or the Generalitat de Catalunya, NGO networks such as Fundacion or QuorumGlobal, cooperatives like Somenergia, or the National Commission for Public Debate (Commission Nationale du Débat Public) in France.</p> <p>http://www.euocities.eu/euocities/documents/Decidim-barcelona-WSP0-AZ9ATM</p>
<p>Participative City Making project (Rotterdam, NL)</p>	<p>The aim of the <i>Participatory City Making</i> project is to develop a framework that can enhance participatory city making of the various groups. In particular, the project explores the interaction between grassroots initiatives and the public administration through small-scale experiments. Collaborative construction of new visions through small-scale experimenting, as a way of triggering a process of broader change and transformation, are studied within a Transition Management perspective.</p> <p>In the city of Rotterdam, the case study context, the project aims at uncovering unique insights and governance issues by analyzing the opportunities, challenges and barriers for Participatory City Making. A new toolset will be developed that should enable heterogeneous stakeholders to participate actively, explore the collaborative envisioned potential, and articulate their own role in the new city making process. This development of the toolset will contribute to the understanding of the value of prototyping for systemic change.</p> <p>The project is developed by the TUDelft in collaboration with the Dutch Research Institute for Transition and the Hogeschool Rotterdam.</p> <p>https://participatorycitymaking.nl/</p>

As previously mentioned, applying this participatory approach in rural areas is an uncommon practice. However, RURITAGE strives to change this situation by activating as many local actors as possible, also making leverage on ‘local heroes/leaders’, meaning well-known local people who are well considered in their community and who can play a key role in the engagement of other citizens within the Hub.

Section 2

RURITAGE approach for activating, managing and monitoring Rural Heritage Hub: role, functions and ideas

Introduction to the Rural Heritage Hub concept

To ensure that the research and resulting strategies for heritage-led rural regeneration embed the experience and knowledge of all stakeholders, RURITAGE aims at involving all members of society and motivate them to participate in civic, social, economic and political activities at local level. For this, a local RHH will be established in each RM and R to be the main ground of innovation and discussion with stakeholders to develop, implement, and monitor the heritage-led rural regeneration plans.

RHHs are social spaces, communities of stakeholders at local level, **embedded in physical spaces** where knowledge transfer and sharing and other project related activities will take place. Physical spaces have already been defined for Replicators at proposal stage. The final locations of the Hubs for both RMs and Rs are included in this deliverable in Section 2.4.2.

One coordinator per Hub has been appointed and will be responsible for smooth running of the Hubs' activities and permanent contact with the engaged stakeholders. The RHHs will have slightly different objectives and functions for Rs and RMs:

RMs	Rs
<p>The Hub shall gather together key actors at local and regional level, following the typology development proposed in this deliverable, and shall engage those stakeholders that contributed to the success of the strategies already in place with the objective of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - better understanding key success factors and encountered difficulties, and - further enhance ownership of cultural heritage by learning from other RMs. 	<p>The Hub shall involve key actors at local and regional level, following the typology development proposed in this deliverable, with the aim of co-developing and co-implementing heritage-led rural regeneration plans. Particular attention will be dedicated to the involvement of residents.</p>

Hubs undergo different stages of development from their launching to their end of life although the dynamics of different communities can be very distinct from each other. In the following sections the processes of each stage of community development and engagement is described and concrete recommendations for Hub coordinators are provided.

Starting a Hub would be to determine the primary intent of the community (scope and kind of knowledge it will share), to define the domain and identify engaging issues (topical and social boundaries; aspects of the domain community members might be passionate about), to build a case for action, identify potential coordinators and thought leaders and create a preliminary design for the community.

A critical and often underestimated role is the one of the **community coordinators** - in RURITAGE 'Hub Coordinator' - who is a crucial factor for the success of co-creation process. The coordinator should identify important issues, plan and facilitate community events, informally and actively link

community members, help build the practice etc. Another key figure to be considered as a driver for fostering active and true participatory processes at local level is **the ‘local leader’**, as also mentioned in Deliverable 3.1 – Guidelines for stakeholders’ identification and engagement. The local leaders can be well-known and respected representatives of local communities who shall be engaged within the Hubs. They can potentially reach both local residents and organisations and institutions. Examples of local leaders are the priest, the school teacher, the doctor, the pharmacist, successful farmers or any other respected and recognised person at local level.

The main issue in the second stage of community development is to generate enough energy for the community to develop relationships and sufficient trust to discuss genuinely problems and discover what knowledge should be shared and how. During this stage communities are often particularly fragile, as the energy of starting the new endeavor often has already gone while stable structures and cooperation patterns have not yet developed. The role of the coordinator is particularly important in this stage. A typical work plan in this phase would be to initiate community events and spaces, build connections between core group members, find the ideas, insights, and practices that are worth sharing; and identify opportunities to provide value. RHH phases:

Figure 2 – 3 phases for RHHs

Phase 1- Setting up the Hub

- Definition and role of the RHH local coordinator
- Identification and refurbishment (if needed) of the physical Hub
- Community engagement and identification and engagement of stakeholders
- Activating the Hub as a multifunctional space

Phase 2 -Activities in the Hub

- Launching of the Hub
- Rs’ activities in the Hub
- RMs’ activities in the Hub

Phase 3 Monitoring the Hub

Phase 1- Setting up the Hub

1. Definition and role of the RHH Coordinator

The role of the **Hub coordinators** is fundamental to ensure the effective and smooth organisation and implementation of the activities and events of the RHHs. One coordinator is established in each Hub and she/he will be responsible for providing inputs for discussion and to guiding stakeholders towards the co-development of the heritage-led rural regeneration plans. In particular the **functions** of Hub coordinators include:

- Responsibility of the work related with the hub refurbishment, whenever needed
- Coordinating the identification/recruitment of the stakeholders of the Hub
- Launching the physical and social Hub space at M10
- Coordinating all the logistics of the Hub (meetings, invitations, reports, etc)
- Knowledge brokering
- Maintaining constant dialogue and contact with the stakeholders and informing them about project progress and main results
- Creating trust in the project and in RURITAGE consortium and maintaining it for the entire duration of the project
- Coordinating communication and dissemination activities of the RHH
- Maintaining close connection with RURITAGE Knowledge Facilitator Partners and WP2 and WP3 leaders
- Reporting on the activities implemented in the Hub and monitoring the proposed indicators
- Guaranteeing the compliance to Data Privacy and ethics requirements.
- Collecting agreements and informed consent forms of participants

To ensure good communication and exchange of knowledge and experiences within the Hub, the coordinator shall have:

- ✓ **Critical appraisal skills:** capacity to appraise evidence to evaluate its quality, importance and applicability to a particular context. In addition to traditional critical appraisal skills, the Hub coordinators should have a minimum knowledge of the sector, the broader environment, its key players and controversies – and use this to gauge the applicability and adaptability of new evidence to users' contexts.
- ✓ **Communication skills:** strong oral and written communication skills. Coordinators should use active listening skills to gain insight into the interests, issues and innovation of the Hub members.
- ✓ **Mediation skills:** capacity to assemble teams and foster collaboration amongst individuals and groups who would not normally work together. Coordinators should be able to reconcile misunderstandings, facilitate the identification of shared goals, and negotiate mutually beneficial roles for all group members.
- ✓ **Previous relevant experience in facilitation processes and education:** it is recommended that the Hub coordinators have previous experience in education (formal/non-formal) and/or facilitation/coordination of teams or groups. They shall be able to work with people with different ages, cultures, backgrounds and to recognise the group's dynamics and behavioural styles and foster interaction and participation of all members of the Hub. Other

important skills to be considered are, on one side, soft skills - flexibility, ability to create an inclusive environment, enthusiasm, active listening, time management, neutrality – and, on the other side, technical skills (especially qualitative data gathering), and facilitation skills for co-creation.

According to this description each R and RM has appointed its own Hub coordinator at the start of the project (see *Annex III*). Some of the partners will also contract a facilitator to carry out the activities within the Hub (costs for this task are foreseen under subcontracting budget line).

In order to build specific skills among RHH coordinators and to come up with successful co-development of regeneration plans by Rs, RURITAGE has foreseen to implement a **mutual learning and mentoring process** where both RMs and Rs can exchange experiences to upskill and reskill their knowledge and capacities. WP1 is meant to result with a good practices Repository and an inventory of lessons learnt available from RMs and a Replicator Baseline with challenges identified (May 2019), which will serve to Rs as a basis for the co-development of effective and innovative regeneration plans to be implemented at local level. Also, RMs and Rs will have the chance to meet physically and exchange on their experiences. On one side, a **series of workshops** will be organised by WP2 Leader UNESCO in the framework of Task 2.3 from M9. The aims are to reach and train on heritage-led rural regeneration the wider stakeholder community of RURITAGE across the different RMs and Rs and to ensure capacity building to guarantee knowledge transfer and brokerage across different SIAs and different RHHs. At least 4 workshops of 3-4 days will be organised:

1. **Training workshop (M10):** This workshop will foresee a training for the coordinators of the Replicators' RHH regarding this CHMP methodology implementation. This training will ensure that the Rs' coordinators will experience co-creation methods in first person, putting themselves in stakeholders' shoes to be better prepared to take on their role in their RHH. In particular, during this event, the pilot version of the RURITAGE serious game developed within Task 2.2 will be tested for the first time. The training will also be an opportunity to work on RHH coordinators' soft skills (flexibility, ability to create an inclusive environment, active listening, time management, neutrality) and technical skills, such as qualitative data gathering, facilitation skills for co-creation and for the implementation of RURITAGE serious game.
2. **Development workshop (M12):** During this workshop, the main theme of the development and the implementation phase will be discussed. Thematic sessions will be organized on business model development, fund raising (including crowdfunding), and investment, start-ups incubation and possible funding opportunities, participatory governance and communication and dissemination. The RHH coordinators will also be trained on RURITAGE DSS use
3. **Launch workshop (M18):** This workshop will be organized to support the Rs in the launching of the implementation phase. Thematic plenary and bilateral sessions with the Replicators will be held to verify and further support them in the starting phase of the implementation.

4. **Fine-tuning workshop (M30):** The feedback will be crucial to fine-tune the implementation efforts of Rs. This workshop will allow Rs to present the projects they are implementing and to receive feedback and further suggestions from the consortium and other relevant project external bodies.

These events will be a key opportunity for Rs and RMs to gather together, also with other project partner, and receive dedicated training for their Hub activities. On the other side, within the framework of these trainings, bilateral meetings will be also foreseen to give Rs the opportunity to exchange more closely with dedicated RMs, whose good practices could be replicable in Rs' own area.

2. Identification and Refurbishment of the physical Hub

2.1 Hubs in Replicators

RHHs established within the Replicators will act as a **living lab of open innovation and co-creation** through the participation of a wide range of stakeholders in the development, implementation, and monitoring of the heritage-led rural regeneration strategies. At proposal stage each Replicator already identified its own SIA of interest and also possible interesting practices to put in place by learning from relevant RMs.

All the Rs have already identified the physical space where the activities of their Hubs will take place. The table below provides an overview of the locations that have been chosen by the partners. Some of them are still in definition, so changes could take place before the official launch of the Hub.

Replicator		Physical space identified	Pictures
R1	Old traditions & modern world along the pilgrimage route to Hemmaberg (Austria)	Geopark info center	
R2	A brand for discovering local food products and traditions in Rogalangen (Norway)	Old protected library of Egersund, built in 1850	
R3	Working with CNH as a way for migrants' integration in Geo-N (Germany)	Headquarter of Geo-N (historic building in the city center of Lorsch)	
R4	Festival of love – arts connecting heritage and tradition (Slovenia)	Negova castle built between the 11th and the 12th century	
R5	Social innovation & local traditions to react after a disaster in Marche region (Italy)	Old primary school of Appignano, now used as auditorium	
R6	Integrated Management of Mandra Geopark in Gediz-Bakircay Basin (Turkey)	Old primary school in the village of Yukaribey	

An overview of the SIAs, CNH areas and activities planned for each R is provided in *Annex I*.

2.2 Hubs in Role Models

Within RMs, where the heritage-led strategies have already been developed and implemented, **the Hubs will include stakeholders that contributed to the development and the implementation of**

the strategies, to gather their expertise and make it available for the Rs. Moreover, both within RMs and Rs, the RHH will contribute to foster and secure citizen's engagement and ownership of culture heritage. On the one side, RHHs will be the place to investigate and further boost the social innovation potential related with heritage in a participatory and co-creation process, while, on the other side, they will be at the core of the capacity building and mutual learning approach, ensuring knowledge and skills transference from RMs to Rs and among RMs themselves.

Each RM belongs to one of the six SIAs identified in the project. At proposal stage each RM identified its own good practices to be shared with Replicators and it selected a number of actions to be discussed within the Hubs and later implemented based on the experiences of other RMs. In *Annex II* an overview of this information is provided. RMs will be mentoring Rs in the definition of their own effective actions and strategies for the co-development of the regeneration plans, based on the experience of the RMs and the lessons learnt by them and collected in WP1.

3. Community engagement and establishment of the community Hubs

Within D3.1 and D3.2, task leader CE and RMs and Rs, with the overall coordination of UNIBO, ICLEI, UNESCO, Savonia, NMBU and CRS, have drafted **guidelines for community engagement** and they have undertaken a comprehensive stakeholder analysis, drawing upon the resources and support of RURITAGE RMs and Rs. A network of stakeholders that will serve as the cornerstone of the activities of the RHHs has been identified per each RM and each R and included in D3.2 – Stakeholder database, whose final version will be released at M10. Such stakeholders list will be considered as a 'live' database that will be improved, tailored and increased until M10 and, whenever possible, even beyond thanks to the partners dissemination activities.

D3.1 defines the profile of stakeholders to be involved in the co-development, co-implementation and co-monitoring of the RURITAGE regeneration plans and it provides overall guidance for their successful engagement from the establishment of the Hubs until the end of the project. The proposed approach entails four phases, summarized in the figures below:

Figure 3 – RURITAGE approach for community engagement

3.1 Stakeholders' profile

To ensure a wide range of visions and opinions in the discussion within in the Hubs, four functional areas – **Policy, Research, Public/User, Industry/Services/Investors** - have been outlined in D3.1 – Guidelines for stakeholders and, according to these, a list of the most important groups of stakeholders to be involved in the Hubs defined.

Figure 4 – Stakeholders' profiles identified

Policy

- Regional and local governing bodies and institutions with responsibility for territorial development, territorial planning, urbanism, management of CNH sites/buildings, tourism, education, culture, innovation, environment, employment/work, disaster risk management, etc.

Public/User

- Schools and other education and training centres.
- Civil society organizations, especially those focussed on management of CNH sites/buildings, art and performance, tourism, education, environment, youth, etc.
- Local Action Groups.
- Museums and libraries.
- Individual citizens interested in the management of CNH, tourism, education,

Research

- Universities and/or research institutes engaged in research relevant for the project such as CNH governance/management, territorial development, territorial planning, architecture,

regeneration processes, earth sciences, economics, governance, sustainable planning, cultural and historical studies, social sciences, applied sciences, applied business research, etc.

Industry/Services/Investors

- Representatives of key value chains according to the SIA's specificities, such as tourism value chain, cultural and creative industries value chain, food value chain, arts and crafts etc.
- Public investors, such as institutes or centres for territorial development, heritage,
- Private investors, such as banks, sponsors, foundations, etc.
- Key service providers in rural areas, like transport, education, health, leisure, mass media, telecommunication and ICT etc. Service providers differentiate from representative of key value chains since those can include both for profit and no profit organizations. Even in the case of for-profit organizations, in most cases the main aim of service providers is not profit making or profit maximization (this is the case for instance of hospital and other public health providers, schools or other education organizations).

The mapping based on the above-mentioned categories is described in detail in D3.1, tailored and shaped with specific consideration of the needs and objectives of the different RMs and Rs and their SIAs of interest.

3.2 Inviting and recruiting members of the Hubs

The active participation of members of the RHHs are one of the most important factors for the project's success and effectiveness. Therefore, Hub coordinators, in charge of managing the Hubs and communicating with stakeholders, shall invest in a thorough identification of potential Hub members participants and **invitation and recruitment process**.

With the support of the RURITAGE partner in charge of project dissemination, a number of steps to approach local communities have been foreseen in D3.1. In particular, for the purposes of the present deliverable, it is relevant to mention the following points:

- **Step 1: Prepare an initial information set in the local language**
The starting point of communication with local stakeholders must be the preparation of information materials in the local language, including leaflets / flyers and a list of potential questions that. The consent form and information sheet models that have been provided by the Ethic Advisor shall be translated and made available. All the material is available in the shared repository of the project.
- **Step 2: Identify and engage local multipliers**
'Multipliers', i.e. partners that have the capacity to reach out to a wide number of local stakeholders, should be identified. The local multipliers should be approached directly, and sufficient efforts should be invested in engaging them into the RHH (as participating stakeholders or at least as supporters). Once such partners share the vision and goals of the RHH, they will contribute to RHH formation by distributing information through their channels and inviting their contacts to join the RHH.

- **Step 3: Reach out through existing actors and channels**
Rs should rely on channels and actors that already exist in their areas. Rs are encouraged to rely on own local experience. Furthermore, informal communication with the members of stakeholder groups would be very helpful, (i.e. simply asking them what the best way to reach out to their organisations/institutions is). In this sense, a strategy would be to identify ‘local leaders’ – well-known and respected representatives of local communities – and to invite them as the RHH stakeholders and local multipliers, since they can potentially reach both local residents as well as local organisations and institutions.
- **Step 4: Organise Info Days**
When contacting stakeholders as presented above, it is recommended to invite them to an Info Day where detailed information about RHHs will be presented. During the Info Day, the stakeholders should be invited to join the RHH.

4. Hubs as multifunctional spaces

RHHs are not only social spaces, but also physical places where to meet and exchange ideas, practices and experiences. Through the collective community-management in place within the Rural Heritage Hubs, RURITAGE will gather stakeholders and local communities in a new form of collaboration, engaging them in a participatory and community-based heritage management and planning. In the longer run, efforts have to be put into sustaining the community. Communities usually come to a natural end, either by changing contexts rendering the community’s domain irrelevant, by resolving the issues that united the community, or by simply fading away, losing members and not finding enough commonality to hold the community together anymore. In this sense, **making the physical space vibrant and alive with other activities not directly related to RURITAGE is a crucial part of the sustainability of the Hubs and of the innovative participatory process.** Giving multiple functionalities to the Hub space will ensure that the local community uses the space in a continuous manner and will create a strong sense of ownership, leading to building a stronger and closer community, which is one of the main objectives of the project itself.

In recent years, the creation of multifunctional spaces has become a common practice in urban contexts. However, this is a rather unexplored territory in rural areas, and RURITAGE sets the basis for the creation of such spaces, which will allow building a sense of ownership from the local community’s perspective.

As a starting point, RMs and Rs should put great efforts in engaging a wide range of different actors and the civil society as a whole in order to involve and empower them to actively participate in the participatory process. **Engaging actors that are not directly related to the RURITAGE activities in the creation and use of these physical spaces will facilitate their interaction with the project itself** since they will become more aware of the project activities and chances of them participating in these will increase. As an example, these actors could be required to participate in the project’s dissemination in exchange for the use of the physical space of the Hub. In sections 4.1 and 4.2 indications on the different type of stakeholders that could be involved and how to engage them in

the participatory process are provided. **Ensuring that Hub spaces remain useful and lively beyond the end of the project must be a priority** since these will allow the establishment of communities of interest to promote cultural and natural heritage at local level. Following, there are some practical suggestions to be considered for a successful Hub creation and maintenance during and after the project's lifetime:

1) Physical structure:

Each Hub will present different physical characteristics and the feasible activities that could be performed in that space will depend highly on this fact. Therefore, before organizing a specific activity it must be considered whether the physical space is suitable. The maximum space capacity for people to participate in the participatory activities is also a factor to be taken into account when selecting an appropriate Hub location.

2) Community calendar and opening times:

A community calendar should be put in place in order to organize the different activities, RURITAGE related or not. This calendar must be easily available to all target groups, online and offline for those without access to internet. Furthermore, the most suitable opening times to attract more people must be considered, which will depend greatly from the local context.

3) Communication material in the Hub

Given that the Hubs are recovered and/or renewed by the project, mandatory communication and dissemination materials should be put in place in a permanent manner to both promote the project and attract more potential interested actors. This material will include, for instance, posters and leaflets that will be designed and included in the communication pack developed in WP7.

The following represent some examples of different uses that could be given to these spaces to keep them vibrant and useful when project activities are not taking place:

- Co-working space
- Newspaper library with "internet point"
- Literature club activities
- Book exchange point
- Repair café
- Second hand market
- Handcrafts workshops
- Sewing class
- Wellness spot (yoga, pilates or fitness lessons)
- Language courses
- Dance lessons
- Movie nights
- Theater lessons
- Chess club
- Business meeting center (Rural meeting)
- Photography workshops

These activities not directly related to RURITAGE that could be organized or the different uses that the local community could give to the Hub space will depend on each local socio-economic context. For instance, demographic characteristics can be a relevant factor when considering the use to be given to the Hub space in the sense that some activities will be of interest to some target groups and not to others. Close collaboration with local associations is key to identify the potential activities to be organized.

Phase 2 Activities in the Hub

1. Launch of the Hubs

Once the stakeholders identify and engage the relevant stakeholders, the **Replicators** will need to **officially open the Hub space at M10 (March 2019)**. Replicators and Role Models will organize a first open public event, following the guidelines provided in this deliverable (see following paragraph) and the Local Communication Plan developed within Task 7.1. The RHH will then become the place for co-developing, co-implementing and co-monitoring the actions in the following tasks.

It is worth highlighting, as previously mentioned in section 2.4.2, the importance of engaging the local community in making use of the physical Hub location for other activities not directly related to the project. In this way, these spaces will become vibrant and alive with a wide range of activities and events targeting as many different groups as possible. RMs and Rs must put efforts on this point from the beginning of the establishment of the RHHs.

2. Local Activities in the RHH

2.1 Exchange between Rs and RMs

Exchange and mutual learning between Rs and RMs represent the basis of the RURITAGE paradigm and effective implementation of the foreseen activities. The knowledge transfer and capacity building methodology among RMs and Rs can be expressed by the Tree metaphor, reflecting the dynamic and bilateral relations happening between Rs and RMs.

On one side, RMs and Rs have been selected at proposal stage according to their expertise and interests related to one precise SIA. At the same time, Rs already demonstrated the willingness to benefit from the experiences and the knowledge of RMs from other SIAs, in a knowledge environment able to nurture the entire Rs ecosystem.

RMs play a fundamental role in the phase of Hub activities' implementation and co-development of regeneration plans for Rs. To fulfil this aim, **WP1** is expected to make available in May 2019 a **comprehensive inventory of all the lessons learnt by RMs along with baselines for Rs with main identified challenges**. This will serve as basis for Rs to start thinking about the co-development of their plans. Also, from M9 **Rs will be mentored and supported by the relevant RMs** in the activities

Figure 5 – RURITAGE Tree

they will have to organize. Rs will have the chance to exchange with RMs in dedicated **bilateral meetings** and at the same time to receive **specific training** for the effective co-development and co-implementation of their strategies. Rs will be invited to visit RMs and their RHHs and will also have the occasion to host the RMs in their own Hubs.

The process of knowledge transfer is not intended to be unidirectional (RMs>Rs), but it should be considered as a dynamic exchange of capacities to swap experiences in a fertile environment to improve their knowledge and capacities. RMs will be able to share good practices with other RMs and learn more about other SIA of interest. Likewise, Rs will have the opportunity to mutually exchange tips on the development and implementation of their plans with other Rs and to share good practices already implemented, as impetus for their growth.

2.2 Activities in the replicators

The objective of this phase is to involve the local stakeholders and all the civil society in a participatory process of co-development and co-implementation of the heritage-led rural regeneration strategies. Based on the main SIAs of interest of the Rs and on the activities predefined at a proposal stage, each **R will have to discuss those in a critical way, leaving room for additional ideas and proposal coming from the RHH participants**. The co-development process will last **seven months** and will involve a wide range of different activities explained in detail below. In all this process the technical partners of the consortium and in particular UNIBO, CE, ICLEI, SAVONIA and CRS will closely follow the Replicators.

RMs will be also quite crucial in this phase. Indeed, as from M9 Rs will be mentored and supported by the relevant RMs in the activities they will have to organize. Rs will be invited to visit RMs and their RHHs and will also have the occasion to host the RMs in their own Hubs.

RURITAGE Rs will have to organise a number of dedicated activities within their engaging representatives of their local communities. One Hub coordinator has been identified at the start of the project and will be responsible for the smooth running of the activities organised within the Hub space and for the communication with WP leader and the Coordinator.

Each Hub will have to convene in a number of activities, among which some had already been identified at proposal level and others (co-creation activities) are established in the present CHMP.

During the phase of co-development of the regeneration plans, **the Hub coordinators of the Replicators shall organise at least the following events:**

- one open event to launch the Hub officially and involve local residents within the RHHs (Task 3.1)
- one workshop with the integration of RURITAGE serious games
- one participatory workshop
- one event to define business models (Task 3.2)
- one round table with the key stakeholders to set the regeneration plans
- one event inviting potential investors and drafting voluntary agreements
- one final event to launch the implementation phase

Figures 6 & 7 – Timeline for co-development and co-implementation of regeneration plans

2.2.1 Co-development of regeneration plans

Hub activation activities

Type of activity	Overall objective	Deadline
Hub activation activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Overall online and offline dissemination of the RURITAGE project and Hub activities at local level - Contact with and invitation of key stakeholders identified according to the guidelines for stakeholder engagement (D3.1) - Hand out information sheets - Signature of informed consent templates by the stakeholders that agree to participate in the Hub activities - Work on the hub as a multifunctional activator space: discuss with local association about their need in terms of physical spaces and try to set the Hub for this purpose too. 	All RURITAGE duration, until May 2022
Release of stakeholder database for deliverable 3.2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - List of stakeholders that agreed to participate in the Hub activities before the launch of the Hub. However, the database should be intended as a 'live' document to be updated during the project since stakeholders and citizens could be also recruited after the official launch of the Hub and throughout the duration of the co-development, co-implementation, co-monitoring of the regeneration plans. 	February 2019 (until the end of the project, May 2022)

Launching event of the RHH (for both RMs and Rs)

Short description	The launching event will represent the official introduction of RURITAGE to the local community and rest of stakeholders. It will be an occasion to present the Hub space itself and the activities to be implemented throughout the project.
When	March – April 2019 (before 15 th of April)
Where	Local Rural Heritage Hub. If the RHH has rather limited space, the organisers might host a part of the event in another location close-by or in an open space next to the Hub.
Who	RMs and Rs
General objective	<p>Officially launch Hub space and gather additional stakeholders</p> <p>Raise awareness about the local area and community benefit from the involvement in the RHH and thus in the RURITAGE project. Also, partners would emphasise overarching messages to stress on the benefits the promotion of cultural and natural heritage could generate in their areas (see communication messages developed by ICLEI), in particular:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. improve quality of life of the residents of rural areas; 2. contribute to social inclusion, economic growth and environmental balance in rural areas; 3. make rural areas more attractive for sustainable business development.
Specific targets	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Launch the official Hub space • Present RURITAGE with focus on the role of the Replicator <u>area</u> in the project; • Make clear the expected benefits for the area's participation in RURITAGE project • Obtain support for the RHH • Build a good relationship with the 'local leaders' ('local heroes'). • Present the activity calendar of the Hub, key steps, meetings and deadlines • Involve local community and further disseminate the Hub space and activities at local level • Present specific challenges/objectives (for Replicators only)
Expected results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Updated list of participants in Hub activities • Clear picture of the role of stakeholders in the Hub • Dissemination of RURITAGE at local, regional and national level • Wide visibility of the event (mass media, social media, etc)
Type of event and logistics	<p>Public event</p> <p>No fixed duration for the event (it could be one full day event or half a day according to the stakeholders to be involved and partners' preferences). Partners could consider organising the event over the weekend to be able to attract the civil society.</p> <p>Standard programme:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Institutional greetings 2) Presentation of RURITAGE project including presentation of the partner organization and their role in RURITAGE and at local level (great emphasis should be included on communicating the objective of the project at a local level)

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3) Role of stakeholders and benefits in participating, plus interactive part when participants can meet the RHH stakeholders and interact with them directly. A presentation from regional/local authority could be planned too. 4) Hub foreseen activities 5) Creative workshop to collect insights on local challenges and potential improvements of SIA <p>Apart from the standard programme, dynamic activities related to the SIA of interest should be organized to attract as much people as possible into the event, such as:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) informative stands with tourism providers/offices 2) mini-market with local food, tastings, etc 3) art shows, concerts, traditional dances, theatre for both kids and adults 4) workshops and traditional games for both kids and adults 5) competitions / raffles 6) video screenings <p>Local associations could also promote different activities not related to RURITAGE that will be organized in the Hub location, such as sewing lessons, language courses, etc. Stands or reserved spots for them must be provided considering the characteristics of the Hub space.</p>
<p>Target group and audience</p>	<p>All potential stakeholders, including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy: regional and local governing bodies, territorial development institutions, management of CNH sites, etc. • Public: associations, schools, local action groups, civil society organizations, local residents, etc. • Research: universities and research institutes, etc. Civil society as a whole • Industry/services/investors: representatives of key value chains, centres for territorial development, foundations, transport, health leisure providers, media, press, etc.
<p>Communication and Dissemination of the event (LDP)</p>	<p>Partners shall refer to their own LDP for the dissemination of this activity. However, some additional suggestions are provided below:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Before the event: distribute flyers, leaflets, make posters visible in key locations etc. in info points, local museums, cultural centers, public buildings. Disseminate the event through your own social media channels and also stakeholders' if possible. Involve the 'local heroes' to increase the reach-out effect. Contact the mass media and try to catch their interest. Send out press releases to relevant newspapers. • During the event: place posters, flyers, leaflets and other communication material (bracelets, RURITAGE handcrafts, etc.) in visible spots. Try to involve the local mass media (TV, newspaper,

	<p>etc.). Write quick news bits and share them on social media. Real-time broadcasting through Facebook live could be also considered, if relevant. Take short (1 to 3 min.) video/ audio interviews. Take a group picture with participants.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • After the event: publish pictures, videos and news about your event on the project's website and your own institutional website, on social media and other relevant channels. Send out press releases to relevant newspapers.
Partnership and sponsor	<p>Accommodation providers Restaurants Farming companies Investors Non-profit organizations/associations Artists Handcrafters Universities and research centers Transport providers</p>
Estimated budget and eligible cost	<p>Eligible costs: staff cost and other direct cost.</p> <p>Replicators: We estimate a cost of around 2000/3000€ for the organisation of the event (i.e. catering, printing of dissemination material, facilitator, etc).</p> <p>Role Models: we estimated a cost of around 1500/2000€ for the organization of the event (i.e. catering, printing of dissemination material, facilitator, etc).</p> <p>Each partner has dedicated budget under other direct cost budget line: please check page 42 of the Annex I of the Grant Agreement. Also, partners have staff costs under WP3 to pay their personnel / Hub coordinator and a facilitator, whenever needed.</p>

Serious game

Type of activity	Overall objective	Deadline
Workshop with RURITAGE serious game (dedicated guidelines are developed in task 2.2 and will be presented in separate documents)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Present and discuss RURITAGE Practices and Lessons learnt from Role Models defined in WP1 - Brainstorm on which solutions can work in their situation 	May 2019

Participatory preparatory workshop

Short description	The participatory preparatory workshop will make use of facilitation techniques proposed in the CHMP and it will be open to a larger number of stakeholders with respect to the previous activity (serious game).
When	May – June 2019 after the serious game workshop
Where	Local Rural Heritage Hub
Who	Rs
What	Workshop involving stakeholders in the co-creation of the regeneration plans for Replicators.
General objective	Extend the discussion on regeneration plans to a wider audience and complementing input gained from serious game activity
Specific targets	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discuss the overall objective of the heritage led regeneration strategies • Basing on the RMs' GPs, understanding the benefit that could come from different regeneration strategies • Identify which among the Lessons learned (organized by crosscutting themes) from the RMs could be relevant to the R's area and SIA(s) of interest • Discuss the outcomes of the Serious game workshop • Focus on the local strategy to be adopted within a regeneration plan, identifying at least 5 actions aggregating the identified lesson learned/serious games outcomes • Discuss the RURITAGE brand and its development and usage
Expected results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • List of ideas of regeneration strategies
Type of event and logistics	<p>Workshop Half a day</p> <p>Standard programme:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ice breaking session to get to know participants (see examples of ice breaking exercises in the Annexes of the present deliverable) 2. Presentation of the general objective of the workshop and brief overview on the practices/lesson learned from WP1 3. Co-creation session to generate and collect ideas and inputs from stakeholders exploiting one or more facilitation techniques of the CHMP, based on the outcome of the serious game workshop and the good practices/lessons learned from RMs identified as relevant for the replicator 4. Evaluation session to summarise the generated ideas and choose the most relevant ones to come up with possible strategies for final regeneration plan (see examples of games&tools for evaluation and assessment in the Annexes of the present deliverable) <p>A facilitator can be foreseen to lead the discussion, if needed.</p>
Target group and audience	<p>All potential stakeholders, including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy: regional and local governing bodies, territorial development institutions, management of CNH sites, etc.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public: associations, schools, local action groups, civil society organizations, local residents, etc. • Research: universities and research institutes, etc. • Industry/services/investors: representatives of key value chains, centres for territorial development, foundations, transport, health leisure providers, etc.
<p>Communication and Dissemination of the event (LDP)</p>	<p>Partners shall refer to their own LDP for the dissemination of this activity. However, some additional suggestions are provided below:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Before the event: disseminate the event through your own social media channels and website and also stakeholders' ones, if possible. Involvement of 'local heroes' will increase the reach-out effect. Send out press releases to relevant newspapers. • During the event: place posters, roll ups, flyers, leaflets and other communication material in visible spots. At the same time, it would be also good to have some 'live' dissemination of the event on the social media, posted on the accounts of the partner organisation and by tagging the project accounts and using hashtags, if relevant. Take short (1 to 3 min.) video/ audio interviews. Take a group picture with participants. • After the event: publish pictures, videos and news about your event on the project's website and your own institutional website, on social media and other relevant channels. Send out press releases to relevant newspapers.
<p>Partnership and sponsor</p>	<p>Accommodation providers Restaurants Farming companies Transport providers</p>
<p>Estimated budget and eligible cost</p>	<p>Eligible costs: staff cost and other direct cost.</p> <p>We estimate a cost of around 1000€ for the organisation of the event including catering, material for co-creation session (i.e. flip board, post-its, pens, etc) and printing of dissemination material. Rs can consider hiring a facilitator for this type of event.</p> <p>Each partner has dedicated budget under other direct cost budget line: please check page 42 of the Annex I of the Grant Agreement. Also, partners have staff costs under WP3 to pay their personnel / Hub coordinator.</p>

Event to define business models

Type of activity	Overall objective	Deadline
Event to define business models (dedicated guidelines are developed in task 3.2 and will be presented in separate documents)	- Define innovative business models and gather feedback for compilation of Deliverable 3.3	June-July 2019

Round table with the key stakeholders

Short description	Round table with selected key stakeholders to define the final regeneration plan to be implemented.
When	August – September 2019
Where	Local Rural Heritage Hub
Who	Rs
What	Round table for final definition of the regeneration plan.
General objective	Draft tailored plans to ensure they are consistent with R's context and objectives
Specific targets	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Drafting the different actions/activities include in the plan • Defining roles and responsibilities of the stakeholders in the implementation of the actions • Build the PPPs to be drafted • Understanding the financial issues that could be raised • Understanding how to foster the creation of possible start-up companies that could raise
Expected results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regeneration plan drafted and ready to be presented to the investors in October 2019
Type of event and logistics	<p>Round table Half a day</p> <p>For this event a standard programme hasn't been foreseen yet. It will be tailored based on the Rs ideas for regeneration plan and could vary in format and numbers (bilateral meetings with key stakeholders could also be foreseen for the implementation of specific actions).</p> <p>As a general recommendation, based on the outcomes of the participatory planning and the business models workshops resulting with the definition of a range of specific actions and business models, Rs will develop 1) final interventions to be included in the plans, 2) define related stakeholders' roles, 3) agree on which types of PPPs will need to be drafted and which are the financial issues to be taken into account. In this session, partners can exploit one or more facilitation techniques of the CHMP to gather input from participants.</p> <p>A facilitator can be foreseen to lead the discussion, if needed.</p>

Target group and audience	Key and most active stakeholders at local level
Dissemination and marketing of the event (LDP)	<p>Partners shall refer to their own LDP for the dissemination of this activity. However, some additional suggestions are provided below:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Before the event: contact key stakeholders individually well in advance in order to ensure their availability for the event. In parallel, disseminate the event through your own social media channels and website and also stakeholders' ones, if possible. • During the event: place posters, roll ups, flyers, leaflets and other communication material in visible spots. Write quick news bits and share them on social media. Take short (1 to 3 min.) video/ audio interviews. Take a group picture with participants. • After the event: publish pictures and news about your event on the project's website and your own institutional website, social media and other relevant channels. Disseminate the news about final release of the plans on local press (television, radio, and/or newspapers).
Partnership and sponsor	<p>Accommodation providers Restaurants Farming companies Transport providers</p>
Estimated budget and eligible cost	<p>Eligible costs: staff cost and other direct cost.</p> <p>We estimate a cost of around 1000€ for the organisation of the event including catering and printing of additional dissemination material, if needed.</p> <p>Each partner has dedicated budget under other direct cost budget line: please check page 42 of the Annex I of the Grant Agreement. Also, partners have staff costs under WP3 to pay their personnel / Hub coordinator.</p>

Event inviting potential investors

Short description	Event for potential investors and drafting of the public-private (or public-public) partnerships
When	October 2019
Where	Local Rural Heritage Hub
Who	Rs
What	Event for potential investors and drafting of the public-private (or public-public) partnerships
General objective	Attract and engage investors, draft partnerships and fine tune the regeneration plans, if needed
Specific targets	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentation of the drafted regeneration plan to gather additional feedback for its fine-tuning and attract investors. • Receiving tips from crowdfunding expert or other innovative to build a crowdfunding or match-funding project

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure the feasibility of the plan to be implemented. • Drafting of voluntary agreements (i.e. public-private partnerships, public- private-people partnerships a public-people partnership) to be set up for the effective implementation of the regeneration plan.
Expected results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public-private / public-public partnerships drafted • Modifications to the regeneration plan if needed
Type of event and logistics	<p>Round table Half a day</p>
Target group and audience	Key stakeholders and potential investors
Communication and Dissemination of the event (LDP)	<p>Partners shall refer to their own LDP for the dissemination of this activity. However, some additional suggestions are provided below:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Before the event: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) direct communication campaign (establish contacts with the potential investors well in advance: contact them directly and if possible organise a b2b meeting to present them the project and engage them) 2) launch a call for interest in local newspapers, websites and social media • During the event: place posters, roll ups, flyers, leaflets and other communication material in visible spots. Foresee some ‘live’ dissemination of the event throughout the day on social media (tag the project and use relevant hashtags). Take short (1 to 3 min.) video/ audio interviews. Take a group picture with participants. • After the event: publish pictures and news about your event on the project’s website and your own institutional website, social media and other relevant channels (newspapers / local media).
Partnership and sponsor	<p>Accommodation providers Restaurants Farming companies Transport providers</p>
Estimated budget and eligible cost	<p>Eligible costs: staff cost and other direct cost.</p> <p>We estimate a cost of around 2000€ for the organisation of the event including catering and printing of additional dissemination material, if needed.</p> <p>Each partner has dedicated budget under other direct cost budget line: please check page 42 of the Annex I of the Grant Agreement. Also, partners have staff costs under WP3 to pay their personnel / Hub coordinator.</p>

Final event to launch implementation phase

Short description	The final event will represent the official presentation of the co-developed regeneration plans to the local and the official launch of the implementation phase.
When	November 2019
Where	Local Rural Heritage Hub
Who	Rs
General objective	<p>Present the co-development phase's results, the activities implemented within the Hubs in the previous months.</p> <p>Launch the implementation phase presenting the heritage-led regeneration plan and present the next steps and activities.</p> <p>Sign public-private and public-public partnerships</p> <p>Raise awareness of the advantages of the adoption of a participatory process for the development of the regeneration plans and of benefits that these will be generated on the local territory.</p>
Specific targets	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Present the final regeneration plan and set the next steps and deadlines for its co-implementation and co-monitoring • Sign voluntary agreements necessary to effectively implement the regeneration plans • Disseminate the project and the plan, give it relevance at media/press level
Expected results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Final regeneration plan presented to a wider audience • Dissemination of RURITAGE at local, regional and national level • Partnerships signed • Update of the stakeholder database, if relevant
Type of event and logistics	<p>Public event</p> <p>One day duration (from 9 to 16)</p> <p>Standard programme:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Presentation of RURITAGE project 2) Present the regeneration plan 3) Presentation from one stakeholders and one citizen? 4) Explain past activities and next steps and deadlines for implementation and monitoring of the plans 5) Sign partnerships <p>Apart from the standard programme, some dynamic activities tailored to the actions foreseen in the regeneration plans shall be organised as a way to complement the standard presentation and to attract more the local audience. Suggestions for tailored activities to be organised will be provided to Rs and RMs based on the co-development phase outcomes.</p>
Target group and audience	<p>All potential stakeholders, including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy: regional and local governing bodies, territorial development institutions, management of CNH sites, etc. • Public: associations, schools, local action groups, civil society organizations, local residents, etc.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research: universities and research institutes, etc. • Industry/services/investors: representatives of key value chains, centres for territorial development, foundations, transport, health leisure providers, media, press etc.
<p>Communication and Dissemination of the event (LDP)</p>	<p>Partners shall refer to their own LDP for the dissemination of this activity. However, some additional suggestions are provided below:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Before the event: distribute flyers, leaflets, make posters visible in key locations etc. in info points, local museums, cultural centers, public buildings. Disseminate the event through your own social media channels and also stakeholders' if possible. Involve the 'local heroes' to increase the reach-out effect. Contact the mass media and try to catch their interest. Send out press releases to relevant newspapers. • During the event: place posters, flyers, leaflets and other communication material (bracelets, RURITAGE handcrafts, etc.) in visible spots. Try to involve the local mass media (TV, newspaper, etc.). Write quick news bits and share them on social media. Real-time broadcasting through Facebook live could be also considered, if relevant. Take short (1 to 3 min.) video/ audio interviews. Take a group picture with participants. • After the event: publish pictures, videos and news about your event on the project's website and your own institutional website, on social media and other relevant channels. Send out press releases to relevant newspapers.
<p>Partnership and sponsor</p>	<p>Accommodation providers Restaurants Farming companies Investors Non-profit organizations/associations Artists Handcrafters Universities and research centers Transport providers</p>
<p>Estimated budget and eligible cost</p>	<p>Eligible costs: staff cost and other direct cost.</p> <p>We estimate a cost of around 2000/3000€ for the organisation of the event (i.e. catering, printing of dissemination material, facilitator, etc).</p> <p>Each partner has dedicated budget under other direct cost budget line: please check page 42 of the Annex I of the Grant Agreement. Also, partners have staff costs under WP3 to pay their personnel / Hub coordinator.</p>

2.2.2 Phase 2: Co-implementation and co-monitoring of regeneration plans

The co-implementation phase itself will last from January 2020 until May 2022 (end of the project) and will involve the participation of the wide range of actors involved in the co-development of the regeneration plans in each Replicator's area as well as of new ones engaged in the process at a later stage. The activities detailed below represent only some of the activities that will take place during the co-implementation phase, since these will be better defined in other WP3 deliverables. For its part, activities for co-monitoring will be defined by the work carried in WP4. Thus, some of activities that shall be organized by each Replicator's coordinator corresponding to the co-implementation of regeneration plans are the following:

- one promotional event to boost RURITAGE marketing strategy
- one event aiming at supporting the inclusion of migrants / vulnerable groups
- one local event to disseminate RURITAGE activities related to community outreach
- one event specific to the Replicator as outlined in the individual regeneration plan
- one event for preparation for the project fine-tuning workshop

Phase 2: Co-Implementation of regeneration plan		
Implementation of RURITAGE marketing strategy	- Each RHH will build storytelling to promote its CNH	December 2019 – May 2022
Event to support inclusion of migrants /vulnerable groups	- Support inclusion migrants and other vulnerable groups within RHH	December 2019 – May 2022
Event to disseminate RURITAGE activities related to community outreach (Task 7.4)	- Reach the local community in the R - Boost creativity and knowledge about RURITAGE within local population	December 2019 – May 2022
Other events specific to the R as outlined in the individual regeneration plans	- Monitor and assess the implementation of the plan	December 2019 – May 2022
Local event for preparation for the project fine-tuning workshop	- Feedback collection from stakeholders to fine-tune each R's implementation phase. This feedback will be reported to the SIB and other partners and assessed during the project fine-tuning workshop at M30.	November 2020 (M28)

2.3 Methods and tools for Hubs' co-creation activities

The Hub coordinators shall make use of the co-creation methods and tools defined in the present document, especially Replicators when organising the participatory planning event and the round table with key stakeholders. Overall, **the choice of the co-creation methods shall be subject to finding a balance among the following criteria:**

- ✓ objectives of the activity
- ✓ thematic topic of focus of the event to be organized and its content
- ✓ type of information the Hub coordinator wants to obtain
- ✓ participants' group
- ✓ time available for the method and for the entire event as well
- ✓ venue of the event
- ✓ level of knowledge and training that the participants need for using the method
- ✓ availability of resources and materials required to implement each method

The co-creation methods shall be aided from structured proceedings and visual techniques which can further help participants to communicate and rationalise their ideas. The RURITAGE approach for the selection of tools and techniques is based on issues which have been highlighted as key success methods in previous EU funded H2020 projects (CIPTec, IC-Health, URBAN-WASTE).

Following the **three-phase structure** proposed in the figure below, several methods and tools that serve the objectives of each stage are described subsequently. The Hub coordinators, with the help of Consulta Europa if necessary, shall pick the co-creation methods that they think it would be best to employ. The figure below presents the methods for the introduction, core co-creation activity and evaluation phases that are proposed to the Hub coordinators.

Figure 8 – Three phase structure for co-creation sessions and relevant co-creation tools and methods

2.3.1. Methods and tools for the introduction phase

In co-creation activities it is important that participants connect one with another. After the introduction of the schedule, activities, and goals of the event, an ‘ice-breaker’ exercise should follow to introduce participants to each other. Such an exercise is intended to help participants begin the process of forming themselves into a team and warm up the group. Organisers will clearly determine beforehand the information each participant needs to know (e.g. name, profession, experience in the field, reasons for attending, aspirations from participation, etc.). Some ice-breakers that can be used in the workshops’ introduction phase are provided in *Annex IV*.

2.3.2. Methods and tools for the core co-creativity session

After the introduction, the second stage of the co-creation activity will take place. This stage constitutes the core co-creativity session and it is the phase in which the innovative concepts will be developed. A selection of appropriate method(s) that stimulate creative thinking and encourage participation will be made by the workshop organizers. Typically, this stage will start with the moderators giving a description of the applied method(s) and making sure that all participants have understood how this works and what is expected from them.

The full set of proposed co-creation techniques that could be used in the co-creativity sessions can be found in *Annex V*, offering an overview of each method, contexts of use, guidelines for implementation as well as requirements in terms of material and time.

2.3.3. Methods and tools for the evaluation phase

In the last stage a prioritisation and validation of the generated concepts should be made in order to identify the most promising co-created ideas. During the evaluation stage of each co-creation workshop, the generated ideas will be checked and evaluated with regard to some predefined criteria. These criteria will be determined according to the workshop’s objectives as well as to the priorities of the respective organizer and location. As such, the evaluation criteria of this phase might vary among the different workshops.

In the framework of the evaluation phase, the Hub coordinators will also foresee time to reach a consensus on the final ranking of the concepts and discuss why some of them are ranked in a low position. Some common methods for evaluating the co-creation concepts are described in *Annex VI*.

2.4 Activities in the Role Models

The **Hub coordinators of the Role Models shall organise at least the following events:**

- Practices Repository workshop to tailor the practices identified in WP1 and agreeing with the stakeholders on the results of that process.
- One opening event to launch the Hub officially and involve local residents within the RHHs (Task 3.1)
- Further activities to be agreed with each RMs

Figure 9 – Timeline for activities in RMs’ Hubs

Practices Repository workshop

The practices repository workshop will be held in all RMs at the beginning of 2019 between January and February. The aim of the workshop will be to present, discuss and agree on identified best practices from WP1 in the RM’s area to better understand key success factors and encountered difficulties and to further enhance cultural heritage ownership of local stakeholders. Stakeholders involved in those practices will be invited to gain from them insights on the process, barriers faced, and solutions encountered. TECNALIA and UNIBO will support RMs in better defining the guidelines of this activity, based on the outcomes of the first analysis carried out in WP1.

Hub activation activities and further implementation

Type of activity	Overall objective	Deadline
Release of stakeholders database for deliverable 3.2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> List of stakeholders that agreed to participate in the Hub activities before the official launch of the Hub, to be included in D3.2. However, the database should be intended as a ‘live’ document to be updated from time to time, since stakeholders and citizens could be recruited also after the launch of the Hub and throughout the duration of the project. 	February 2019, until the end of the project (May 2022)
Hub activation activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Overall online and offline dissemination of the RURITAGE project and Hub activities at local level 	All RURITAGE duration, until May 2022

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Contact with and invitation of key stakeholders identified according to the guidelines for stakeholder engagement (D3.1) - Hand out information sheets - Signature of informed consent templates by the stakeholders that agree to participate in the Hub activities - Work on the hub as a multifunctional activator space: discuss with local association about their need in terms of physical spaces and try to set the Hub for this purpose also 	
Open even for launch of the Hub (see detailed description in the previous section)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Launch the official Hub space - Present RURITAGE - Present the activity calendar of the Hub, key steps and meetings and key deadlines - Involve local residents and further disseminate the Hub space and activities at local level 	May 2019
Tailored activities for each RM's context	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Variety of activities to be defined with each RM 	June 2019 – May 2021

2.5 Dates and duration of Hub activities and tips for RHH coordinator

Hubs' activities for the co-development of the RURITAGE regeneration plans have to be carried out **from M10 (March 2019) to M18 (November 2019) in the Replicators**. Starting from M19 (December 2019) until the end of the project the plans developed will be implemented in the Replicators through the Rural Heritage Hubs. The **Role Models** will implement in the hubs tailored activities to further enhance their heritage-led strategies **from M11 (April 2019) until M36 (May 2021)** working on SIAs other than the one they represent in the project. The duration of the activities taking place in the Hubs will be mainly determined by their objectives and participants' profiles and needs. As such, the Hub coordinators will define the appropriate duration for each activity that will not dis-incentivize people to participate. During the event, the Hub coordinator can always shorten the duration if the intended results are achieved in advance. When it comes to selecting the dates, the Hub coordinators shall avoid clashes with public holidays as well as with days close to public holidays or close to activities that might be of interest to their participants. However, whenever relevant (especially for the public launch event of the Hubs) RMs and Rs could assess the possibility of hosting such a type of event over the weekend to attract a wider audience. This will be up to each RM and R to identify the best timing for the organisation of their activities.

This planning shall be also complemented with discussions on the Digital Heritage Hub, since the participants of the offline activities will be also invited to join and interact on the online platform.

The final version of this digital hub will be integrated within the open and inter-operable online data platform “**RURITAGE Resources Ecosystem**”, which is developed within WP5. In the meantime, while the platform is under development, discussion and knowledge sharing will be encouraged on the [RURITAGE Facebook Group](#). Depending on the topics and interests of the group, subgroups on more specific topics such as SIAs or cross-cutting themes can be created. For early engagement a Facebook group is more advantageous as most RURITAGE members do have a Facebook account, so it is a familiar concept and easy to use. In general people check their accounts several times a week, so this will encourage interactions. Moreover, dedicated webinars will be hosted on Google+ Hangouts on Air. Within Google+ Hangouts on Air webinars can be easily recorded and even edited afterwards. This way we can share the webinar as a replay for those who were not able to attend. The replays can be shared through a YouTube channel or on the “RURITAGE Resources Ecosystem” platform.

2.6 Logistics

When preparing the event, partners shall take into account several aspects that may require the Hub physical space to have certain characteristics, among which we highlight:

- ✓ Availability of appropriate technical infrastructure
- ✓ Sufficient space to hold the number of participants as well as for the selected methods to be performed optimally
- ✓ Appropriate lighting and adequate air circulation and temperature
- ✓ Comfortable and flexible seating and light tables so that the set-up can be adjusted
- ✓ Enough wall space or freestanding surfaces for hanging posters so they can be seen by all participants
- ✓ Quiet and safe place
- ✓ Easy access and proximity to public transport

Lunch and/or coffee breaks could be served to avoid participants’ fatigue. Material for the co-creation activities will be needed, such as flip charts, post-it, pencils, blank sheets, etc. (according to the chosen co-creation methods). In general, the Hub coordinators will make sure that the required material is available at the time and place of the events. In addition, organisers will ensure that the layout and combination of visual elements is sufficient and the most appropriate for their co-creation activities.

2.7 Follow-up activities

Short **reports for dedicated events organised by the Hub coordinators** will be drafted including relevant information about the activity carried out, such as number of participants, the team and their roles, the methodology and material used, a description of the main ideas and outcomes generated, the agenda of the event, the tools used for event dissemination, etc.

The reports will be compiled using Google Forms by each Hub Coordinator. CE and UNIBO will collect all the information throughout the process of co-development, co-implementation and co-

monitoring of the heritage-led regeneration plans and participatory process.

In particular, the aspects of the Hub activities that will be documented into a comprehensive report that will follow the following format and include the following aspects:

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Event agenda according to which the event unfolded
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Information about the participants, i.e. stakeholder groups attending the event, invitation criteria and number of attendants. Signature lists will be kept at RM/R's premises and will be not shared with any other partner. Similarly, personal data will be not mentioned in any of the reports.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A short description of the overall structure of the event phase including the process followed and the co-creation methods used (if any).
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A short description of the key emerged concepts, good practices, ideas, experiences, suggestions for the content and structure of the project innovative heritage led plans/strategies.

Furthermore, after the organisation of dedicated co-development activities, the **stakeholders will be asked to fill in a short questionnaire which will aim to assess the main aspects of the event and to offer an overall evaluation of the event.** These assessment questionnaires will be anonymous and stakeholders taking part into the activities will be encouraged to compile them after the organisation of the activity. The questionnaires will be made available either in Google Form or on the project website. Special attention will be paid to the assessment of some of the activities for co-development of Rs' plans and RMs' strategies. In particular, stakeholders of the Rs will be invited to report on the serious game, the event on business model, the participatory planning event, and the event with investors. On their side, RMs' stakeholders will be encouraged to provide feedback about the organisation of the practices repository workshop to get input for the organisation of the following meetings and, if relevant, about the organisation of other tailored activities. The monitoring and reporting activity will be tailored with WP4 procedures.

Phase 3 Monitoring the Hub

1. Monitoring procedures and indicators

Monitoring activities will aim at assessing the efficacy and efficiency of the participatory process of the RHH. They will include assessment of quantitative aspects and quality aspects. For qualitative assessment participants will be asked to fill in a **questionnaire** (see *Annex VII*) asking for their feedback on the following issues: pre-event organisation and other logistical aspects, objectives, speakers and facilitators, methods, tools and material used, quality of emerged co-created concepts, level of interaction among participants. Quantitative assessment deals with the number of events organised and the number of stakeholders engaged. The table below reports the minimum number of indicators that will be monitored for the Hubs' activities. The monitoring and reporting activity will be tailored with WP4 procedures.

Activities	Indicators
Open events for the launch of the Hubs	Number of participants Number of local associations involved
Co-creation activities organised per R / RM	Number of activities and participants Type of stakeholder groups involved according to the ones identified in D3.1
Co-creation methods used by Hub coordinators for the organisation of the co-creation activities	Number and type of methods/tools
Members recruited within the Hubs	Number of <i>active</i> participants (per gender) participating in the Hub activities Number of <i>passive</i> participants: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of people subscribed to the newsletter • Number of people following/liking the project Facebook and Twitter pages • Number of people registered in the dedicated Hub Facebook group
Users registered in the Digital Hub	Number of users
Online interactions on the Digital Hub	Number of discussions initiated
	Number of posts
Social media interactions	Number of posts/pictures mentioning the Hub
	Number of posts mentioning RURITAGE at local level

Section 3

RURITAGE Rural Heritage Hub: useful materials and tools

1. Digital Heritage Hub: Online tools for Hubs' communities

With the increasing presence of information and communication technologies, particularly the Internet, the way we communicate and share information is undergoing fundamental changes. Without doubt this has also changed the way communities are organised.

Wenger and colleagues (2009) speak of '**digital habitats**' where communities dwell. All the three dimensions structuring a community – domain, community and practice – place demand on technology while at the same time available technology opens up new facets of each dimension (Wenger et al. 2009). Technologies thus may extend and reframe the way communities are organised in significant ways. It changes the way boundaries are expressed and also enables a large group to exchange ideas and practices – but at the same time it also offers new opportunities for small and highly specialised though maybe dispersed groups.

Wenger and colleagues suggest four perspectives to make sense of the ways technologies can be experienced as a habitat by a community such as RRHs:

- ✓ The tools that support specific community activities and that refer to an identifiable piece of technology that supports a discrete activity in a community.
- ✓ The platforms into which vendors and developers package tools.
- ✓ The features that help make tools and platforms usable and 'liveable'.
- ✓ The full configuration of technologies that sustains the habitat (which is rarely confined to one platform).

Communities learn together in different ways: some meet regularly, some converse online, some work together, some share documents, some develop deep bonds, and some are driven by the mission they serve. Wenger et al. (2009) present a rich portfolio of activities and relevant tools for these different types of communities in their book and provide guidelines on how technology stewards may proceed to match technology support with the interests and activities of community members.

Within the framework of RURITAGE Hubs a series of online tools shall be exploited to maximise the engagement of stakeholders and support participatory process locally. First of all, a **Digital Rural Heritage Hub (Digital RHH)** will be used by RMs and Rs and stakeholders invited to join the digital environment. The Digital RHH will be

Figure 10 – Digital Habitats by Wenger

used by RMs and Rs and stakeholders invited to join the digital environment. The Digital RHH will be

conceived as an open blog for discussion, accessible per SIA and per the cross-cutting themes. The local coordinator of the RHH will be responsible to give access of this tool among its local stakeholders: there the stakeholders can share and exchange ideas on possible actions to be implemented during the co-development phase of the heritage-led regeneration plans.

Additionally, **social media tools** shall also be exploited as a useful technique to communicate with stakeholders. In particular, social media shall be used for each type of stakeholder: Instagram and Facebook are the most adequate instruments to reach citizens but not the best channels to reach organizations (Linked-in and Twitter are probably the best instruments). Partners are encouraged to make use of the Facebook channel where the tone is more personal than on Twitter and, in order to get followers and reach a wider audience, they can invite friends, connect with RURITAGE website and FB account, and target followers of your institutional account. A Facebook group for each Hub will be established for each Hub and maintained alive by the end of the project and if possible beyond. Stakeholders engaging within the Hub will be invited to join the group and the Hub Coordinators will keep track of posts, new users, number of likes, and periodically report those to CE, UNIBO and ICLEI for dissemination purposes.

Beside the social media, partners might also rely on other digital channels, since not all people use social media. In this regard, we highlight the relevance of **online (local) press and media** such as online newspaper, radio and TV.

2. Dissemination and communication of the RHH

Rs will outline Local Communication Plans (LCP) adapting the overall project approach for dissemination and communication to their own needs and specificities. All the **dissemination efforts for the promotion of the Hubs** and their activities shall be in line with the LCP. In addition to this, the present deliverable wants to provide some general guidelines for the dissemination of the Hubs' activities taking place within the Rs and the RMs before, during and after the events to be organised.

○ **Before the event**

Partners should start the dissemination of their Hub activity at least three weeks before the event. On one hand, partners will hand out dissemination materials (brochure, poster, leaflet) before the event and disseminate the event through their usual local dissemination channels (institutional websites and social media, press releases, newsletters, etc). For any doubt on this matter, partners shall refer to ICLEI - the dissemination leader of the RURITAGE project. On the other hand, online dissemination shall be pursued at both project and R/RM level.

○ **During the event**

The Hub coordinator or her/his collaborator(s) shall take pictures during the local event. At the same time, if possible, it would be good to have some 'live' dissemination of the event on the social media to be posted both on the Twitter and/or Facebook account of the Rs/RMs in charge of the co-creation activity and on the project Twitter/Facebook accounts. Real-time broadcasting live could be also considered, if relevant.

○ **After the event**

The Hub coordinator or her/his collaborators shall publish pictures and news about their event on the project's website and their own institutional website and other relevant channels. They can also send out press releases to relevant newspapers and reach other relevant local media (radio or television).

Key dissemination tools should be exploited by responsible partners, Rs and RMs in order to reach a wide audience, and in particular:

Project website	A page dedicated to the Hubs and to the Digital Hub might be foreseen on the website. Moreover, the link to the platform will be shown in the browsing banner on the homepage.
Partners' websites	Partners will promote their Hubs and the Digital Hub through their respective websites.
Newsletters	The references to the Hubs' activities and to the link to the Digital Hub will be included in project newsletters.
Project social media & partners' social media	Information on the online community will be posted on social media: both on the project official accounts and on partners' ones.
Media/press releases	Information on the Hub activities and results shall be disseminated also through media and/or press releases.

3. Potential risks and proposed solutions for a better management of the Hub

In the table that follows some indicative risks that can emerge during the preparation of the activities in the Hubs or even during the event day have been outlined with respective actions for addressing them.

Undesirable Situation	How to prevent it	How to manage it
<p>Participants do not confirm. <i>When participants do not confirm a sense of uncertainty develops during the preparation of the workshop</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Make the invitations in the right way ✓ Make confirmation easy ✓ Keep in contact ✓ Keep a reserve list 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Insist on confirmation ✓ Use the reserve list

<p>The participants who have enrolled do not arrive on time</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Take care with the invitation and the enrolment and confirmation processes ✓ Provide assistance for getting to the venue ✓ Send the agenda beforehand ✓ Generate commitment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Postpone the opening session of the workshop to allow time for people to arrive ✓ Start and decide at what stage it is no longer viable for late arrivals to join
<p>The participants fail to work with a proposed tool</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Explain the procedure clearly from the start ✓ Assist and support the participants at the whole time of the event/session ✓ Provide tools which are easy to use, effective and save time ✓ Prepare alternative tools 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Present and explain the reason for this particular tool ✓ Remain calm: the tool is there to aid the workshop and should not be defended to the point of exhaustion ✓ Choose an alternative ✓ Change this tool for another if the group agrees
<p>The participants are passive</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Make sure that all participants feel free to express their opinion. Some of them may feel that they lack the necessary expertise and will be reluctant to share their ideas and perspectives ✓ Find out about the participants' interests and commitment when organizing the workshop. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Propose working in smaller groups to increase participation ✓ Use tools and activities that encourage interaction ✓ Find out the reasons for the passive behaviour so that you can find the means of securing their participation

The group appears tired	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Choose a comfortable place ✓ Use several exercises as energizers ✓ Plan some time for non-scheduled small breaks ✓ Keep sessions within time limits in order to ensure that the workshop ends on time 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Propose activities to liven up the group and keep it alert ✓ Keep your sense of humour ✓ Have spontaneous breaks
Aggressive behaviour of one participant towards another person in the workshop	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Agree rules for behaviour and interaction ✓ Identify possible conflicts in advance ✓ Watch the participants' body language ✓ Be neutral and avoid judging ideologies, values and beliefs ✓ Be an example; treat everyone equally and in a friendly way 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Talk to the parties involved, remind them of the wellbeing of the workshop and suggest a time to speak ✓ Look for assistance within the group

4. Ethics and data protection aspects

This paragraph, drafted by the RURITAGE Ethical Advisor, outlines key ethics and data protection aspects relevant for the implementation of the activities within the Hubs, also in accordance with the provisions set in D3.1. Project Information Sheet is included in Annex IX of the present document, while the Project Informed Consent Sheet can be consulted in D9.2.

Being ethical in dealing with humans and their personal data in social and human sciences research projects means above all to be fully transparent towards them.

All stakeholders who will be involved in the RURITAGE project will be duly informed in advance about the project and what their participation implies. In research projects there is often some uncertainty and lack of specialised knowledge about information to be provided to humans, via “informed consent/assent forms” and “information sheets”. We would like to clarify this aspect as concerns the RURITAGE project.

On the one side, there is the **information concerning the project objectives and activities** and the involvement of volunteers. This has the purpose of clarifying all relevant issues to support prospective participants, enabling them to make an informed decision, such as the voluntary character of participation, the possibility to withdraw at any time without any adverse consequences, the role that participants will play, etc. We will call the document containing this information “**Project Information Sheet**” (PIS).

On the other side, there is the specific information which must be provided to comply with applicable rules and regulations on the protection of personal data, in particular Regulation No. 2016/679 (General Data Protection Regulation), as well as national and local rules which integrate and complete it. Such information is partly different from the one provided to create awareness of the project and regarding project participation. Providing this information is of the utmost importance, as - in its absence - personal data processing would be unlawful. We will call the document containing this information “**Data protection Informed Consent Form**” (ICF).

Both sets of information will have to be provided to stakeholders in an effective, not just formal way. The problem of information sheets is that they are often regarded to as a nuisance and accepted without being read. Too much information too often equals no information. There is thus a trade-off between the ethical and legal obligations of transparency, which impose to write a lot of information and content, and the need to be concise, clear and understandable for the reader.

The legal basis for personal data processing in the RURITAGE project is the data subject’s explicit consent. Participation within the Hubs will take place entirely on a volunteer basis and the Rs and the RMs indeed will obtain and clearly document participants’ informed consent in advance. Any documentation given to them will be timely, clear and comprehensive, and there will be an opportunity for them to raise any issues of concern and ask for advice or further explanations.

It is at the participant’s discretion as to whether she/he wishes to participate in the Hubs’ activities or not, thus all participants will be **volunteers**. Considerable care should be taken where consent is sought from those in a dependent position (i.e. vulnerable people, such as migrants and people with disabilities). In this sense, in the informed consent document it will be made clear that refusal to participate will not lead to any adverse consequences.

The Hub coordinators will ensure that potential participants have fully understood the information and do not feel pressured or coerced into giving consent. The template of info sheet can be found in the *Annex IX* of the present document, while the template of informed consent is available in D9.2.

Annex I – Summary of preliminary R’s SIA, CNH and practices of interest

R1_ Old traditions & modern world along the pilgrimage route to Hemmaberg (Austria) – ARGE GK (PP34)		
SIA	Pilgrimage	
CNH in the area	Archaeological, settlement and art heritage, chapels and castles, historic routes, technical heritage of mining and ethnologic heritage.	
Possible practices	Protection and development of cultural and natural pilgrimage points on Hemmaberg / Route digitalization / Eco-tourism promotion / Training & capacity building activities	RM1, RM2
	Support local business and young entrepreneurs to invest in the area	RM4
	Promote festivals and art events to create awareness and job opportunities	RM7, RM8
R2_ A brand for discovering local food products and traditions in Rogaland (Norway) – Magma UG		
SIA	Sustainable Local Food Production	
CNH in the area	Geological and landscape features; agriculture, fishing and sheep and cattle farming methods and traditions; historic buildings.	
Possible practices	Local producers support and networking / Products standards definition, labelling and branding / Process and products innovation	RM3, RM4
	Rediscover the Coastal Pilgrim Route “Kystpilgrimsleia”	RM1
	Training, internships and involvement in local festivals for migrants’ integration / Viking play / Collaboration with local actors to provide a joined cultural offer	RM5, RM6 RM7, RM8
	Interactive exhibitions and awareness raising on hazards and landscape interactions	RM9, RM10
R3_ Working for CNH as a way for migrants’ integration in Geo-N (Germany) – Geo-N (PP27)		
SIA	Migration	
CNH in the area	Geological and landscape features; historic settlements and routes (dating to the Celts and Roman periods); heritage related to the mining.	
Possible practices	Internships for refugees in Geo-N’s maintenance team Rangers and Guides / traditional agriculture / environment protection / Educational programs	RM5, RM6
	Support festivals and art events to promote awareness, attract visitors and to build a community of interest	RM7, RM8
	Mapping cultural landscape elements / Landscape conservation projects and trainings for staff, refugees and locals	RM12, RM13
R4_ Festival of love – arts connecting heritage and tradition (Slovenia) – KULTprotur (PP24), KIBLA (PP23)		
SIA	Arts&Festivals	
CNH in the area	Negova Castle; historic settlements, agri-food traditional products and fairs; landscape features, craft old methods and traditions.	

Possible practices	New local businesses related to food and crafts, new marketing strategies&branding	RM3, RM4
	Organization of Festival of Love 2018 as driver for related events, and activities all year long / new sets of tourist packs / promote the discovering of the territory	RM7, RM8
R5_Social innovation & local traditions to react after a disaster in Marche region (Italy) – CoApp (PP30)		
SIA	Resilience	
CNH in the area	Landscape features (badlands), historic villages and churches, agri-food traditional products, art (i.e. music) and craft old methods and traditions.	
Possible practices	Disaster response training for local communities / Toolkit of the resilient citizens / Co-monitoring and co-management system / Creation of a new symbolic public space	RM9, RM10
	Trainings for local producers to foster innovation and sustainability	RM3, RM4
	Valorization project for the "Path of the Blue-Grey Badlands"	RM1, RM2 RM11, RM12, RM13
	Promotion and implementation of local music festival	RM7, RM8
R6_Integrated Management of Madra Geopark in Gediz-Bakircay Basins (TK) – IZM, DEM, IZTECH (PP36-38)		
SIA	Integrated Landscape Management	
CNH in the area	Geological and landscape features; archaeological features and heritage sites, agri-food traditional products, historic routes old towns and villages	
Possible practices	Geotrail and Geocycle routes / Visitor Centre & Research Centre- Promotion&Communication Activities / Public Utilities	RM11, RM12, RM13
	Local food festival-hub as a training and social centre for cooperatives of farmers	RM3, RM4
	Promotion of craft production and marketing / Cycles of local festivals / Provide opportunities for all ages and abilities	RM7, RM8

Annex II – Summary of RM’s practices, evidences and SIAs of interest

RM1_ Camino de Santiago (Spain)	
RM practices:	• Establishment of associative bodies for effectively manage the Way at local level • wide restoration of old buildings along the Way production and marketing of local products • deep research on CNH • CNH Digitalization and Monitoring • Training and employment programs.
RM evidences:	• more than 270,000 pilgrims from more than 100 countries (63% on the French way) total yearly income • 5 new brands and labels for local products • 12 fairs • 750,000 people trained.
SIAs of interest:	<u>PILGRIMAGE</u> <u>RURAL FOOD</u> <u>ART&FESTIVAL</u> <u>RESILIENCE</u> <u>LANDSCAPE</u>
RM2_ MARIA-UT (Romania)	
RM practices:	• Improved services and ICT for pilgrims • promote eco-tourism related to pilgrimage routes • ad- hoc guided tours and travels • Promote a fidelity card to support businesses (networked tourist offer).
RM evidences:	• more than 1,000 km of routes • 480 km mapped and provided with services • 500 students • more than 5,000 pilgrims involved in tailored programs • ARS SACRA Festival involving yearly 400 people.
SIAs of interest:	<u>PILGRIMAGE</u> <u>RURAL FOOD</u>
RM3_Preserving old traditions for innovating agro-food production in Apulia (Italy)	
RM practices:	• Innovation support to local agro-food producers • Creation of food clusters • Marketing strategies • Products standards of quality definition • Sustainable agro-food production • Rural hubs for social innovation.
RM evidences:	• Technological agri-food district involving 100 companies, 12 Universities and Research centres, 14 local administrations • new local business and start-ups • increased visibility of the area and related products (new labels) • products innovation in the agri-food sector • innovative bottom-up approaches.
SIAs of interest:	<u>PILGRIMAGE</u> <u>RURAL FOOD</u> <u>MIGRATION</u> <u>ART&FESTIVAL</u>
RM4_Coffee production in World Heritage landscape (Colombia)	
RM practices:	• Provision of supporting services to fair coffee producers for business management • Digital connections and online training • Inventories and guidelines for the built CH valorisation • Plan for the biodiversity protection • Strategic and action plans for the promotion of the area as a touristic destination.
RM evidences:	• 195,000 tons of coffee produced yearly • 207,000 Ha cultivated within the Coffee Landscape.
SIAs of interest:	<u>RURAL FOOD</u> <u>RESILIENCE</u> <u>LANDSCAPE</u>
RM5_ Migrants hospitality and integration in Asti Province (Italy)	

<p>RM practices: • Rural Hub for migrant’s integration • rehabilitation of Historic buildings for hospitality • training and internships for migrants in CNH field • Integration through CNH (festival, food, etc.)</p>
<p>RM evidences: • 160 migrants yearly hosted in a historic building restored • creation of an innovative social enterprise for rehabilitation of old traditional cultivations with organic techniques.</p>
<p>SIAs of interest: <u>RURAL FOOD</u> <u>MIGRATION</u> <u>LANDSCAPE</u></p>
<p>RM6_ Boosting migrant integration with nature in Lesvos Island (Greece)</p>
<p>RM practices: • integration and information programmes for migrants and citizens • Educational programmes and guided tours, specifically tailored for migrants to make them aware of the CNH of the territory • Agricultural Festival • earthquake simulator</p>
<p>RM evidences: • 200 migrants yearly trained in NHMLPF</p>
<p>SIAs of interest: <u>RURAL FOOD</u> <u>MIGRATION</u> <u>RESILIENCE</u></p>
<p>RM7_ Discovering and making professional performing arts accessible to rural communities living in villages and small towns, Somerset (United Kingdom)</p>
<p>RM practices: • Develop a rural touring network as a way of bringing high quality, professional performing arts experiences to rural communities in community spaces across Somerset • Promote rural touring opportunities to artists and companies • Develop public and local earned income funding strategies to sustain the rural touring ecology • Marketing events in partnership with villages to attract audiences • Build social capital by developing informal education resources for volunteer promoters and information for artists • Overall aim is to provide opportunities for all ages and abilities to experience, participate and work in the arts within a predominantly rural context</p>
<p>RM evidences: • Over 50 art, participation and performance projects in the last 20 years • In 20 years has cooperated with over 750 established companies • In 20 years events have reached over 150,000 audiences • Annually we have 30 promoting groups and 200 volunteers.</p>
<p>SIAs of interest: <u>PILGRIMAGE</u> <u>RURAL FOOD</u> <u>LANDSCAPE</u></p>
<p>RM8_ The Living Village of the Middle Age, Visegrad (Hungary)</p>
<p>RM practices: • Tourists tailored packs • Support local traditional activities (branding, clustering, internationalization) • Networking with other Festivals • Place narrative strategy.</p>
<p>RM evidences: • Around 1,000 performers and 40,000 visitors coming yearly for the Castle Visegrad Games • connections and partnerships with 6 other cities in Europe promoting Historical Festivals.</p>
<p>SIAs of interest: <u>PILGRIMAGE</u> <u>RURAL FOOD</u> <u>LANDSCAPE</u></p>
<p>RM9_ Teaching culture for learning resilience in Crete (Greece)</p>
<p>RM practices: • Resilience training for the community • A toolkit for resilient citizens • Research the traditional practices to increase resilience • Guidelines for risk assessment and mitigation actions.</p>
<p>RM evidences: • More than 1,000 volunteers and local authorities employees trained • 8,500 pupils involved • more than 20,000 visitors experienced the Informative Awareness Project • 4 National Workshop organized.</p>

SIAs of interest: <u>PILGRIMAGE</u> <u>RURAL FOOD</u> <u>MIGRATION</u> <u>ART&FESTIVAL</u>
RM10_ Natural hazards as intangible CNH for human resilience in South Iceland (Iceland)
RM practices: • Traditional storytelling as a mean to understand the environment, foster awareness on the relation among landscape • Participative projects for resilient communities.
RM evidences: • 70-100% of local people trained (5% trained as rescue team members) • 100% locals and tourists (around 200,000 overnight stay in Katla each year) are informed in case of extreme event by SMS.
SIAs of interest: <u>PILGRIMAGE</u> <u>RURAL FOOD</u>
RM11_A CNH-led approach in Austrått manorial landscape (Norway)
RM practices: • Participative process for recognize and evaluate CNH features • An innovative method for integrated heritage management.
RM evidences: • Establishment of an integrated heritage management system • more local business opportunities • increased tourist numbers and employment related to tourism • more safeguard of the landscape.
SIAs of interest: <u>RURAL FOOD</u> <u>ART&FESTIVAL</u> <u>LANDSCAPE</u>
RM12_Douro cultural landscape, driver for economic and social development (Spain)
RM practices: • Changes management: Strategies to evaluate interactions between social and ecological systems • Local businesses empowerment and branding • Heritage Territorial System: a dynamic multi-layered map • Social Innovation Laboratory for CNH • High level training program for landscape managers.
RM evidences: • +300,000Ha of Natura2000 • 20,000 cultural elements and 1,000 historical towns protected • 13 new brands and labels for local products • 110 companies supported • 250 people trained.
SIAs of interest: <u>PILGRIMAGE</u> <u>RURAL FOOD</u> <u>ART&FESTIVAL</u> <u>MIGRATION</u> <u>RESILIENCE</u> <u>LANDSCAPE</u>
RM13_Wild Atlantic Way (Ireland)
RM practices: • Local branding and narrative 'Wild Atlantic way' • Natural and Cultural heritage revalorization • Sport and leisure activities in the nature (surf, hiking, etc.) • Strong integration of art and festival along all the way
RM evidences: • 157 discovery points, 1,000 attractions and more than 2,500 activities along the way • Increased number of tourists in the region • Re-entering of private sector investment in the area
SIAs of interest: <u>PILGRIMAGE</u> <u>RURAL FOOD</u> <u>RESILIENCE</u> <u>LANDSCAPE</u>

Annex III – RHH coordinators

Role Models			
Hub		Name of the coordinator	Experience and skills
RM1	Camino de Santiago (Spain)	Zoa Escudero (FSMLRPH)	Zoa has 20 year-experience in patrimonial and cultural topics, from field work (research, restoration, planning, events, etc.) to the aspects of coordination, monitoring, and control of work teams. She knows quite well the sector involved from a tourism and heritage resource as well as an institutional point of view. Other areas in which she has experience is the didactics and dissemination of history, teaching in higher education, advanced courses and Masters, through the direction of research in the university and research fellows. She considers she has listening skills, for negotiation, to generate an inclusive and friendly environment among different people.
RM2	MARIA-UT (Romania)	Szakacs F Sandor (Pro Edu)	Szakács finished his doctoral studies in Rome in 2006. During his studies he worked with handicapped children in Germany for several years, besides he engaged in journalism from time to time. He was director at Jakab Antal Study House and Salvator Hotel of the well-known pilgrimage site Sumuleu-Ciuc (Csiksomlyo) between 2008-2015. He initiated the foundation of diocesan Association Pro Education - Network for Adult Education and Training in 2010. Since then he is the operative leader of this network and active supporter of creating synergies in Catholic adult education. He contributed to the foundation of Association Via Mariae, now he is responsible for the external relationships by this organization. He used to plan and lead pilgrimages to the well-known pilgrimage sites of Europe, he possesses a national tourist license as well. Furthermore, he is collaborator by several governmental bodies from Hungary (within the Ministry of Human Capacities). He engages actively in fundraising for civil organizations; in advocacy, strategic planning, partnership and project generation. He is knower of Church leadership in Transylvania. He speaks Hungarian, Romanian, German and Italian.

RM3	Preserving old traditions for innovating agro-food production in Apulia (Italy)	Antonio Stasi (DARE)	Antonio Stasi (MSc, PhD). Professor of agricultural economics and policy at the University of Foggia, delegate to the international relationships and cooperation for the Department SAFE. Coordinator of emerging start-ups in the province of Foggia on behalf Apulia Region Agency for Youth Policies. Strategic management at Vazapp project. Experience in International research and educational project. Experience in rural social regeneration.
RM4	Coffee production in World Heritage landscape (Colombia)	Karen Castiblanco Torres (FCM)	Undergraduate studies in Political Science and Government, candidate for a master's degree in Human Rights and Democratization, ample experience in territorial development projects in armed conflict areas. Strong academic knowledge of territorial issues and ability of relating government organizations to design and fundraise for local and national projects. Native Spanish speaker. Proficient in English and French.
RM5	Migrants hospitality and integration in Asti Province (Italy)	Mossino Alberto (PIAM)	President of PIAM onlus, Italian NGO that deals with the reception of asylum seekers, refugees and victims of trafficking in the province of Asti. In 2014 he coordinated the opening of the "Villa Quaglina" refugee reception center in Asti. This reception center has become over the years a socio-cultural center of the city.
RM6	Boosting migrant integration with nature in Lesvos Island (Greece)	Nikolaos Zouro (NHMLPF)	From 2014 Nikolaos coordinates the activity of securing the territory in various municipalities through the employment of the refugees in the maintenance teams. It also deals with local agriculture development and reception of migrants with the agricultural associations in the area.
RM7	Discovering and making professional performing arts accessible to rural communities living in villages and small towns, Somerset (United Kingdom)	Ralph Lister (TA)	Ralph has been leading Take Art as its Executive Director since 1987. He has led the expansion of the organisation from a single focus on rural touring into a multiple cultural agency with dance, theatre, music and eatery years specialisms. Its original remit has extended from Somerset into a regional, national and international dimension, always with a connection with its host area, Somerset. He was a founder member of the National Rural Touring Forum in 1997 (an umbrella organisation for rural touring agencies in England, Wales and Scotland) and served as its chair before becoming its Development Director until 2018.

RM8	The Living Village of the Middle Age, Visegrad (Hungary)	Károly Matolcsy (EMI)	<p>Károly has experience in leadership thanks to his work as a leader of different departments in ÉMI, being the elected president of the Hungarian Roofing Federation and the vice president of ENBRI. He is currently the deputy director for development in ÉMI with 30 years of experience at the company.</p> <p>He is actively participating in different international organisations and is the member of the steering committee of ECTP, therefore he has good communication, networking and organisation skills. He participated in more than 20 EU funded projects, in some of them as WP leader and consortium leader which provided him with good coordination and English skills.</p>
RM9	Teaching culture for learning resilience in Crete (Greece)	Charalampos Fassoulas (UOC)	<p>PhD in Structural geology, Teaching staff at the Uni. of Crete, Curator of Geological Collections at Natural History Museum of Crete, and Scientific Coordinator of Psiloritis UNESCO Global Geopark. Research activities in the fields of tectonic geology, geomorphology, geo-conservation and risk mitigation. Author of more than 70 scientific articles in peer reviewed journals and Coordinator or member of the scientific group of more than 30 applied or research projects. Coordinated EU projects on Civil Protection focussing in raising awareness and training of kids and adults.</p>
RM10	Natural hazards as intangible CNH for human resilience in South Iceland (Iceland)	Hörður Bjarni Harðarson (Katla)	<p>Experience in teaching in the field (snowboarding/skiing), performing music, acting and teaching young children with short attention span. Geological knowledge and residential landscaping experience. Good with people, highly adaptive, communication skills, outgoing, positive and receptive. Good with languages. Flexible. All-round micro-knowledge and inventiveness.</p>
RM11	A CNH-led approach in Austrått manorial landscape (Norway)	Daniel Johansen (NMBU)	<p>Born in Ørlandet and his work has been closely connected to Austrått landscape. He holds a PhD in Art History from NTNU and is the head of the Historic Department at Ørland Cultural Center. Johansen is an active social commentator and historian.</p>
RM12	Douro cultural landscape, driver for economic and social development (Spain)	Silvia Fernández (AEICE)	<p>Master's degree in urban and territorial planning: ability to deal with territorial and urban development projects. Member of AEICE, organization with more than 100 associates and participation in European, national and regional R&D projects, gaining oral and networking skills with multidisciplinary groups plus experience in the organization of national and international</p>

			events (Bimtecnia, ECCF...). Phd candidate with experience in analysis, writing and presentation at conferences, and workshops.
RM13	Wild Atlantic Way (Ireland)	Eunan Cunningham (WESTBIC)	WestBIC Regional Manager for the North West/Border Area of Ireland. Project Initiator and Centre Manager at Fiontarlann Incubation and Enterprise Centre. Provider of Innovation and Business Services to heritage-led, cultural, Irish language and rural enterprise start-ups, SMEs and community organisations. Experienced in working on European and transnational projects. Board Member of the state regional authority for the Gaeltacht, Údarás na Gaeltachta, responsible for the economic, social and cultural development of the Gaeltacht regions of Ireland.

Replicators			
Hub		Name of the coordinator	Experience and skills
R1	Old traditions&modern world along the pilgrimage route to Hemmaberg (Austria)	Darja Komar (ARGE)	Experience in lectures and educational geological workshop implementation for different target groups (children, students, teachers, etc). Experience in project work (INTERREG SI-AT), article writing and group guiding. Communication skills, flexible, and positive.
R2	A brand for discovering local food products and traditions in Rogaland (Norway)	Cathrine Johannessen Skogen (Magma UG)	Teacher with 17 years of experience from Norwegian primary school (year 6 to 13). Main subjects are music, maths and natural/social science. Been studying geology, space technology and GIS/GPS as educational tools in climate change through ESA/NAROM. Born and raised in the Magma UGG Area, and have local knowledge and extensive local network. Used to present, teach and educate both kids and adults.
R3	Working for CNH as a way for migrants' integration in Geo-N (Germany)	Nicole Grünewald-Heller (Geo-N)	Assistant to the Managing Director of the Geo-N, skills in organisation of large events, conference organisation. Gymnastic trainer for children (10-15 years), working with scientists.

R4	Festival of love – arts connecting heritage and tradition (Slovenia)	Peter Tomaž Dobrila (KIBLA)	Producer, (intermedia) artist, curator, mentor, adviser and co-founder of Multimedia Centre KIBLA, Maribor in 1996. Rich experience in NGO sector, and also employed at Ministry of Culture of the Republic of Slovenia as General Director of Directorate for Arts, Member of Minister's Office and Adviser to the Minister. Coordinator of the winning candidacy for Maribor 2012 – European Capital of Culture 2012. Co-initiator of Ljubljana 2010 – World Book Capital (UNESCO) and Maribor 2013 – European Youth Capital. Commissioner for presentation of Slovenia at the 13th International Architecture Exhibition – La Biennale di Venezia, Italy in 2012.
		Katja Bajec (KULTprotur)	Tourist guide and curator, experience with workshops for children, youth and adults.
R5	Social innovation & local traditions to react after a disaster in Marche region (Italy)	Antonella D'Angelo (CoApp)	Urban planner, Technical skills in risk and emergencies management, experience in project management. Trainer in public works education, author of scientific articles.
R6	Integrated Management of Madra Geopark (Turkey)	Demet Burçin Gezgin (IZM)	An urban planner with Master's degree in strategic urban and regional development and sustainable transport policies. After several work experiences with intensive civil dialogue in Istanbul and Dortmund, she has started to work for Izmir Metropolitan Municipality in 2015. Since that time, she participated in transport and spatial development projects and contribute this works with her strong research, analyzing, communication and presentation skills. Native Turkish speaker, proficient in German and English.

Annex IV – Methods and tools for the introduction phase

Standard personal introductions (30 seconds to 1 minute per person)

A display board can be prepared with information that participants will need to know (e.g. name, age, where they are from, occupation, etc.). Each participant will write down their details in the grid on entering the room. Afterwards, each participant reads out his/her personal details to the rest of the room. This display board remains visible throughout the whole workshop. The purpose of this ice-breaker is to start the workshop and for everybody to get to know one another. With defined criteria you can ensure that everyone gives and receives the same basic information.

Variable

Each person gives their name, where they are from and one other fact about themselves. This third fact could be freely chosen by each individual or the facilitator could suggest a theme.

Materials needed

Display board, flipchart and marker pens

Pair introductions/Interviews (up to 1 minute per person)

Participants pair up with another person they do not know. One person interviews the other for 2 minutes, then roles are swapped. Questions could include the reasons why the person is there and what they are hoping to learn or achieve. Then the whole group gathers together and participants introduce their partner to the others, giving as much detail as they can remember. The rationale behind this is to “stir” the group and to provide a more personal connection and deeper understanding between the participants.

Material needed

Paper sheets and pens for taking down notes.

Name games (15 minutes)

The group stands in circle facing each other. Every participant needs to think of a verb (action word) that begins with the same letter as their name. It is better to have an initial round during which everyone says their name, then start off by throwing a (real or imaginary) ball to someone while saying their name and acting out the verb. Of course, the same game can be played without saying the verb.

Material needed

A ball (not compulsory)

The ball of string (20-30 minutes)

This is an exercise that helps participants to introduce themselves and learn the names of the other members of the group. Participants form a circle. The moderator takes a ball of string, holds onto the end of string and says his/her name and without letting go of the string, throws the ball to another person in the circle. The person who catches the ball says his/her name, holds onto the string and then throws the ball to another participant. This sequence is repeated until everybody in the circle is holding onto part of the string and a web has been formed. Once the web is formed, there is also a reflection of the implications of the collective task. The person who ended up with the ball of string passes it back to the person who threw it calling that person's name and so on and the ball of string ends up complete again.

Materials needed

A ball of string

People bingo (20-30 minutes)

The moderator writes down a list of questions that each person in the group will ask the other participants. The question can be specific to the session or generic. Each person should only ask one question to one person then find somebody else to introduce themselves to and ask another question. When they have found answers to all their questions they say bingo and finish. Ten questions get people well mixed and a lot of information shared.

Materials needed

Paper sheets, pens

Annex V – Methods and tools for the core co-creativity session

Brainstorming (30-40 minutes)

Brainstorming stimulates creative thinking and helps gather a large number of ideas from the group as a whole. When a brainstorming session starts the objectives of the session should be clearly stated to all participants. Moderators allow everyone time to write down some ideas (silent brainstorming) before beginning the process. Afterwards, each person expresses an idea or thought and this information is recorded. When using brainstorming a time limit is set, participants offer ideas when it is their turn to speak and any idea is acceptable. Main features:

- ✓ The theme is decided upon and presented and the main question is written up so that it is visible throughout the exercise.
- ✓ The rules of the game are explained.
- ✓ All ideas are accepted. No criticism is allowed of any idea put forward.
- ✓ A timescale is set for the brainstorming session.
- ✓ One or two people are given the task of noting the ideas down on a flipchart or board to be visible to the group as a whole.
- ✓ When the time limit is up, ideas are analysed and conclusions made.
- ✓ The display board can be used as a resource to initiate the use of other planning tools.

Recommendations

Participants need to feel free to express their opinions. All participants must comply with the rules of the game: to avoid more than one person talking at the same time, the facilitator can have participants take turns to make their contribution. This reduces the risk of losing valuable ideas or opinions and allows all members of the group to participate. Participants will need time to warm up and become enthusiastic in expressing new and unusual ideas.

Materials needed

Flip chart, pens and cards

World Café (multiple consecutive sessions of 15-20 minutes each)

The World Café is a creative process for facilitating collaborative dialogue and the sharing of knowledge and ideas in a relatively short time (from a few hours up to one day workshop). A café setting is created, where participants discuss about an issue in small groups around the café tables. At regular intervals the participants move to a new table.

How it is used

- ✓ Participants explore an issue by discussing for multiple consecutive sessions.
- ✓ Participants work in groups of 4-6 people.
- ✓ One of the participants is chosen as the host/hostess of the table.
- ✓ Participants change tables after each session in order to 'cross-fertilise' their discussions with the ideas generated at other tables.

- ✓ After several minutes all participants of each table join another group, except for one participant who remains to brief the next group on what the last group has discussed. The participants that leave their table carry key ideas, themes and questions into their new conversations.
- ✓ By providing opportunities for people to move in several rounds of conversation, ideas, questions, and themes will be linked and connected. At the end of the second or third round, all of the tables in the room will have been cross-pollinated with insights from prior conversations.

Each round is prefaced with a question developed for the specific context and desired purpose of the World Café. The same questions can be used for more than one round, or they can be built upon each other to focus the conversation or guide its direction.

After three or more rounds, the whole group gathers to share and explore emerging insights and concepts, which are captured on flipcharts or by other means. At this point the Café may end and it could be concluded with a final plenary session, where the key ideas and conclusions are established.

Recommendations

The procedure of the method should be clearly explained. Questions to be discussed have to be thought out and clear in order to engage participants. Powerful questions help to attract collective energy, insight and action. People should be reminded to record key ideas, draw thoughts, ideas and questions on the flipcharts that are used as tablecloths. The basic process is simple, but complexities of context, participants and question definition make the presence of an experienced moderator necessary.

Material needed

Tables for 4-6 people each; flipchart paper or paper placemats for covering the tables; multi-colored markers on each table; boards for posting the flipchart papers.

Lego Serious Play (one day or at its shortest three or four hours)

The Lego Serious Play (LSP) methodology offers the means for a group to share ideas, and understandings, to engage in a discussion and to work out meaningful solutions to real problems. Lego Serious Play is a co-creation method, where participants are asked different questions in relation to a specific issue. The participants answer these questions by building symbolic and metaphorical models of their insights with LEGO bricks and by presenting them to each other. The method enables constructive reflection and dialogue processes and gives to people with less expertise and to people who are less vocal the chance to equally participate in a co-creation process.

How it is used

Participants must become familiarised with the process of creating and explaining metaphors using the bricks. Lego Serious Play sessions typically have 4 core phases.

In the first phase and once the participants have become comfortable with the basic building skills and concepts, the moderator poses a question that represents a building challenge to the participants.

In the second phase, the participants build a LEGO model representing their reflections on the question. While building their models, participants assign a meaning to them and develop a story covering the meaning.

In the third phase the participants share the meaning and the story that they have assigned to their model with each other, and listen to the stories of other participants.

In the fourth phase the moderator encourages participants to reflect on what they have heard and seen in the models.

Recommendations

It requires a skilled and experienced moderator. The questions / challenges that are posed to the participants must be open-ended and have no obvious or correct solution. No one in the group has the answer to the challenge and, therefore, LSP is all about participants expressing themselves and listening to each other. This means that there is no right answer to any question.

Material needed

Lego Serious Play kit; Flipcharts; Boards for posting participants' ideas.

Role-playing (one or two hours)

The main goal of role-playing is to make an idea or a scenario tangible enough to elicit a response from the workshop's participants. It helps to understand a subject in more depth, and it also stimulates creativity.

How it is used

- ✓ An idea or scenario that needs to be examined is selected.
- ✓ A situation that represents the theme in question is prepared.
- ✓ Instructions are produced for the different roles in the situation – characters with specific functions, pre-determined behaviours, reactions and positions.
- ✓ The situation that will be acted out is presented to all those taking part in the workshop. The instructions and general information about the task are handed out.
- ✓ Each actor is asked to play the part in the most realistic way possible and according to the particular instructions. The rest of the group makes up the audience and is asked to carefully observe and keep notes on the behaviour, reactions and arguments of the different characters.
- ✓ When the play is over, the situation is evaluated from the notes made by the audience.

Recommendations

A simple role play is the best. The facilitator stops the simulation or roleplay when exercise comes to a natural end, when enough issues have been uncovered or when people want to stop. Participants volunteer and are never forced to play a role they're uncomfortable with. Participants need a few minutes to get into their roles. Anyone who is not playing must be an active observer. After the role play, on one hand, the players state how they felt in their roles; on the other hand, observers provide their impressions and then a discussion follows.

Material needed

Any documentation relating to the role play (information and instructions); enough space; any material required for the role-play; papers and pens to take notes.

Conceptual mapping (individually or in groups; its duration depends on the complexity of the subject)

A conceptual map is used to visually demonstrate the thought process on a chosen subject and to record ideas and their associations. Conceptual mapping is a means of brainstorming and organising thoughts. It facilitates the visual demonstration of brainstorming, it stimulates the generation of ideas and it also allows the creative process to be written up and made available for all to view.

How it is used

- ✓ The map is a schematic drawing with multiple branches.
- ✓ It has a central theme that acts as a starting point, written in the middle, which is the idea that you want to expand or the problem you want to solve.
- ✓ Branches inspired by associations made by participants sprout from the centre. The branches comprise a key image or a key word.
- ✓ Topics of lesser importance are represented as twigs of the relevant branch.
- ✓ Each branch can lead to a flow of new ideas, which are written down as key words, symbols or pictures.
- ✓ As topics and sub-topics emerge, additional associations are made between ideas that aren't necessarily grouped together. These relationships will be noted by using additional lines and arrows.

Material needed

Flipchart and different coloured pens if working in groups; when working individually, one sheet of paper and pencils.

Map-it (half full working day)

Map-it is a participatory mapping method, used to enable the visualisation of a process in an open and flexible manner. It uses a set of icons that allow participants of different backgrounds to equally participate in a co-creation process by clearly express themselves in a visual way. The method can be used for a variety of goals such as co-creation of ideas, evaluation of concepts, break down complex structures and concepts, engagement and equal participation of people.

How it is used

- ✓ Set up a research question and establish a clear goal.
- ✓ Define a well-timed mapping scenario, in which the components of the research question are brought to the surface.
- ✓ If there are more than 10 participants the group should be divided.
- ✓ Each group receives sticker sheets in a different colour.
- ✓ The moderator explains the context, goal and research question of the mapping session.
- ✓ When each group has finished its map, one participant/presenter moves and explains the map to another table which in turn offers feedback and adds to the map.
- ✓ At the end of the sessions, each presenter gives a five-minute summary of the conversation.

Recommendations

During the mapping session, each group needs a moderator who makes sure the mapping session runs smoothly. Summarise the maps and results in a text or a summary map as they would be a good background for a possible follow-up mapping session. The moderator should ensure that time limits are kept.

Materials used

MAP-it kit, pens, documentation material.

Case studies (one hour up to one full working day)

In the case study method, the group gets an opportunity to look at others' experiences in the form of a case. The participants reflect upon these case studies in order to derive new ideas, by using their own experiences, values and feelings as the basis for analysis. Among the reasons for using the case study method is the fact that it exposes the participants to situations they might not ordinarily experience in their own lives and helps to convey complex theoretical concepts in a simple way.

How it is used

A case study related to the workshop's subject should be chosen. Materials should be prepared in a way that allows participants to:

- See the relevance to the subject of the workshop
- See the complexity of the situation
- Understand the dynamics of the specific process
- Understand the motives, actions and reactions of those involved

Clear presentation of the case study to the participants and clear instructions on how to analyse the case study and seek possible solutions should be given. Participants can work on the case in groups. All groups can either begin using the same approach or different groups can look from different perspectives. All groups present their results to the other groups. The whole group draws up conclusions to the results that have been presented.

Recommendations

Instructions given to participants should be clear and enough time should be allocated to the effective implementation of the task. The case study should not be too general but focus on the specific topic of the workshop.

Materials used

Display board, coloured pens, post-it notes, flipchart papers.

Open space Technology (two/three hours at least)

Open Space Technology (OST) was designed as a method for organizing a meeting/workshop where participants create their own program of concurrent work sessions in order to explore issues that interest those most. OST encourages co-creation and self-organisation and allows diverse people to address complex issues.

The process is guided by a moderator who introduces the rules of the technique. Workshop sessions in the chosen issues are self-managed by the participants within a framework of simple principles. Each

workshop session creates a list of required actions and defines any roles that might exist.

How it is used

- ✓ Organisers introduce OST and invite participants to raise a topic they are interested in.
- ✓ Each participant who raises a topic, writes the title of this session, says a few words about the session, and posts it on the wall for all to see.
- ✓ When all issues have been identified and posted, participants sign up and attend those individual sessions. Sessions typically last for half one hour. In case of limited participation in a topic, the participants can join another related topic or drop the topic.
- ✓ After the agenda creation, the individual groups begin their work. People are free to decide which session they want to attend, and may switch to another one at any time.
- ✓ After the opening briefing, the moderator remains largely in the background. However, his/her role remains important as he/she has to create the right atmosphere to engage all participants and make sure that all principles and rules are respected.
- ✓ After the completion of the sessions the group gets together to share what has been generated.

Recommendations

The Open Space method must be based on the following principles:

1. Whoever comes is the right people: this alerts the participants that attendees of a session class as "right" simply because they care to attend.
2. Whenever it starts is the right time: this clarifies the lack of any given schedule or structure and emphasizes creativity and innovation.
3. Whatever happens is the only thing that could have happened.
4. When it is over, it is over: encourages the participants not to waste time, but to move on to something else when the fruitful discussion ends.

Material used

Flipcharts, post-it notes, markers, paper sheets

Phillips 66 (more than 18 participants; at least 45 minutes)

The Phillips 66 method was developed in order to get suggestions, opinions or information from a large group of people in a short period of time, while ensuring maximum participation.

How it is used

- ✓ A participant is set in charge of the overall process.
- ✓ An explanation of the task and the ultimate objective should be given to participants. A subject and a question/problem is formulated to which the groups have to respond.
- ✓ Participants are divided into groups of 6 people. Each group chooses: i) a coordinator whose job is to remind the rest of the group about the time limit and allow each member of the group to put

forward their ideas and ii) a secretary who takes notes and writes down any conclusions (It can be useful to establish the groups in advance of the workshop).

- ✓ Groups have 6 minutes to respond to a question. Then the group discusses what has been identified, analyzes causes and develops possible solutions. The conclusion is recorded by the secretary.
- ✓ Afterwards all groups join together and report back to all participants by presenting their proposed solutions. Each secretary briefly explains their group's conclusions and generated solutions.
- ✓ The secretaries' presentations are summarised on a display board.
- ✓ Discussion starts and a general conclusion is reached.

Recommendations

The question asked should be able to produce a list of answers. Groups can be given up to 15 minutes instead of 6; but if more time is given, there is a risk that a debate will start, instead of just gathering new opinions and information which is the main objective of this method.

Material needed

Flipchart or display board, pens, paper sheets, enough space for each group to discuss the subject without disturbing other groups.

Problem tree (one/two hours depending on the complexity of the problem)

Problem trees are used when complex problems need to be analysed. This method shows the causes and consequences of a problem and helps people identify the aspects that should be tackled in order to achieve significant change.

A problem tree involves writing causes in a negative form. Reversing the problem tree, by replacing negative statements with positive, creates a **solution tree** where the root causes are turned into root solutions. A solution tree identifies means-end relationships as opposed to cause-effects. This provides an overview of the range of projects or interventions that need to occur in order to solve the core problem.

How it is used

- ✓ Problem tree analysis is best carried out in a small focus group of about six to eight people.
- ✓ Clearly formulate the problem(s) that have to be analysed.
- ✓ A central problem is identified and placed in the middle of the tree.
- ✓ Participants are encouraged to identify the causes of the focal problem. These causes are the roots of the tree.
- ✓ Once the causes or roots of the problem have been established, the consequences are identified and become the branches of the tree.
- ✓ The causes and consequences can be created on post-it notes or cards, so that they can be arranged in a cause-and-effect logic.
- ✓ When the task has been completed, the drawing is analysed and a discussion is encouraged to establish whether the organisation of the cards corresponds effectively to the causes and consequences.

The heart of the exercise is the discussion, debate and dialogue that is generated as factors are arranged

and re-arranged, often forming sub-dividing roots and branches (like a conceptual map). Participants should be given time to explain their feelings and reasoning, and record related ideas and points that come up on separate flip chart paper under titles such as solutions, concerns and decisions. Some indicative discussion questions could be the following:

Does this tree represent the reality? Which are the most serious consequences? Which are of most concern?, Which causes are easiest / most difficult to address? What possible solutions or options might there be? Where could a change help address a cause or consequence, or create a solution?

Materials needed

Cards, post-it notes, paper sheets, marker pens, display board, flipchart.

Storytelling (two hours up to one working day)

Storytelling is a powerful technique that has been used for many years in co-creation projects. The method assists knowledge sharing, builds new understanding and triggers people to actively participate. This is achieved as stories can capture and hold the attention, increasing the likelihood of a workshop's participants to contribute in a co-creation procedure. Generally the method can be used as a team building exercise, for problem solving as well as for generating new ideas.

The aspects that should be defined for each story prior to the storytelling session are the following:

- Title of story
- The teller
- The listeners
- Time and place of the story
- Description of the story's characters including their attributes and roles
- The problem and the respective actions

How it is used

- ✓ Establish a theme for the storytelling workshop. It could have a specific focal point or focus on a range of themes. Participants pair up and share their stories.
- ✓ Participants interview their partners, and write down partners' stories, using a story template.
- ✓ Participants form new pairs in order to share their partners' stories to a larger group.
- ✓ Each group of participants report back to the whole group in plenary session.

Recommendations

During the storytelling objects or comic sketches can be used to trigger memories of specific experience as well as to create visual hooks. A variation in the story can be added by using a "what if" question and try to find a solution to newly emerged scenario.

Harvesting (at least one hour)

Harvesting is a hands-on co-creation method used to support the individual and collective meaning making. This method can take either a tangible (documentation, newsletter, audio or video, etc.) or intangible form (new insights, a change of perspective or mindset, a shared clarity, new relationships and contacts) as a means to support innovative idea generation and facilitate decision making.

How it is used

- ✓ Agree on the purpose of the harvesting session and establish some desired outcomes. A clear purpose and some success criteria for both process and the harvest will add clarity and direction.
- ✓ Plan the sessions having in mind the following questions: Who is going to benefit? What form will be most effective? Who should host the harvesting?
- ✓ Conduct gatherings to collect a lot of diverse insights.
- ✓ Use powerful questions which are simple and clear, thought-provoking, challenge assumptions, evoke more questions.
- ✓ Engage in conversation with the participants. The richer the exchange the richer the harvest.
- ✓ Record what is being said and done and create a collective memory (e.g. keep notes, transcripts, participants' documentation, photos, video recording).
- ✓ Harvest results from initial conversations. Then have another session to fill the gaps by inviting everyone to read whatever they want of the documents and select the pieces that seem to have the most relevance and benefit to focal tread of the workshop.
- ✓ Make this second-level harvest visible and begin identifying emerging patter. Create collective sense and meaning.

Go round (at least 30 minutes)

Everyone takes a turn to speak on a subject without interruption or comment from other people. Go rounds are useful for equalising participation and giving everyone some clear space to express their opinion. Allowing people to 'pass' means that no one feels put on the spot. To keep it focused clearly state what the purpose of the go round is and write the question on a flipchart where everyone can see it. Time limits can be set if necessary.

Ideastorms (30 minutes)

A tool for sparking creative thinking and helping to quickly gather a large number of ideas. Begin by stating the issue to be ideastormed. Ask people to call out all their ideas as fast as possible – without censoring them. Have one or two notetakers to write all ideas down write all ideas down. Structured thinking and organising can come afterwards.

Annex VI - Methods and tools for the evaluation phase

Two dimension axis (10-20 minutes)

During this method, participants will place the co-created concepts on a two-dimensional axis that will represent their feasibility and their potential. Through an open discussion and after participants have reached consensus they will place each concept on the two-dimensional axis.

Materials needed

Display board, flipchart, marker pens, post-it notes.

Predefined number of stickers or dots (10-20 minutes)

Dot voting is one of the simplest ways to reach an agreed solution. Each participant is given a number of stickers or dots (1-5 is the usual number). All the co-created ideas are listed on a display board/flipchart. Participants are then asked to cast their votes by sticking their stickers or making their dots by the item/idea that they consider to be the most important. If they have multiple dots/stickers they can have the choice of spending them all in one concept if they feel strongly about it or spreading them across a number of choices. Once all the votes are cast, a list of the items by their new rank is made.

Materials needed

Display board, flipchart, marker pens, stickers.

2-4-8 consensus (at least 1 hour)

This exercise will take time, but it will help reach a decision that everyone supports. Probably it is not suitable for every kind of workshop, but useful for really important discussions. It is better to impose tight time limits at every stage of this discussion, otherwise can easily consume too much time. The procedure of the method is the following:

1. Start in pairs. Each pair discusses the list of options and is asked to agree their top three priorities.
2. Each pair then comes together with another to form a group of four. The two pairs compare their lists of top three priorities and agree on a joint top three.
3. Each group of four comes together with another to form a group of eight. Again, each group takes its two lists of priorities and reduces it to an agreed top three.
4. Repeat until the whole group has come back together. Hopefully three clear priorities have emerged. In the worst case scenario the group has six top priorities and may need to reduce it still further through facilitated discussion or another prioritisation tool.

Materials needed

Paper sheets, pens, flipchart

Thinking hats (at least one hour)

This tool encourages a group to look at a situation from a new angle. Each 'hat' represents a different way of looking at something. There are different ways to do this exercise. For example, individuals within the group can wear different hats whilst the group discuss an issue:

1. One group concentrate on the facts (e.g. what information and knowledge do you know about the situation? What can you learn about the situation from this information? What info is missing? Can you plug the gap?)
2. One group are the emotional input of the discussion. They allow themselves to be intuitive and act as much on hunches as fact.
3. Another group thinks pessimistically, looking for the flaws and finding the obstacles in the plan.
4. Others think positively looking for the value in every possibility.
5. Another hat is worn by the facilitator(s). They concentrate on process, calling on the other hats to add in their thinking as and when it is appropriate and making sure that each option is discussed from all perspectives. They are neutral, helping the group achieve its task without trying to shape the decision.

Another alternative is that everyone in the group can try on one of the 'thinking hats' for a while, then everyone can put on another one. The roles the 'hats' bring give you a chance to thoroughly examine every option and to prioritise or choose the best concept(s). This tool actively seeks out the optimistic analysis, the pessimistic analysis etc., so every idea is thoroughly tested on the basis of a creative and thorough process

Voting system using a Likert scale (10-20 minutes)

A voting system using a Likert scale can be used. This is a ranking system where the participants grade each concept in terms of feasibility, potential, and correspondence to the identified users' needs, using a 10 level Likert scale. It is a rather time consuming method but its results will be accepted by everyone.

InTo tool

Savonia InTo Tool (*into.savonia.fi*) can be used in evaluation of, for example, business ideas. It is a fast internet application applying multicriteria evaluation and decision-making analysis. Using of InTo tool is easy and the results from evaluation will be available right away helping in the prioritizing and selection of ideas to a business model.

Ranking (10-20 minutes)

This is a great technique for using in small groups. Each option is written on a card or post and each group is given a full set of cards/notes. The groups of participants are asked to rank the options or reduce them to three, within a certain time limit. Having a participant to act as a facilitator in each small group will help. It is also helpful to set out clear rules from the start such as time limit, parameters of the evaluation, etc.

Urgent/Important grid (15-30 minutes)

It is a tool that can be applied to facilitate group prioritisation! It can be used on paper, or as a 'Spectrum Line'. The group ranks ideas according to their urgency and importance:

Plus-minus implications (15-30 minutes)

This tool can be used in the whole group, in small groups or individually. The facilitator writes the topic across the top of a large sheet of paper and draws a plus sign, a minus sign and an "I" (which stands for Interesting). By starting with the plus the moderator asks people to list anything that they feel to be positive about the topic and write these without comment around the plus sign. When everyone has had their say the moderator shall move on to the minus sign and list everything that people feel to be more negative.

Around the "I" sign everything that people find interesting shall be written, such as ideas that could be explored further etc. Then the group should move back to the plus sign and start a second round. The first round finds out what is happening with the group. The second round builds upon it. One particular issue can come up in every section as what seems positive to one person could well be negative to the next.

Annex VII – Draft event evaluation questionnaire

CO-CREATION WORKSHOP'S EVALUATION QUESTIONNAIRE				
<i>Please mark your answer</i>				
I. OVERALL EVALUATION	VERY MUCH	MUCH	FAIR	INSUFFICIENT NOT AT ALL
How satisfied are you of the event organised?				
To what extent do you feel confident with the general aims of the project?				
To what extent do consider the involvement of stakeholders/citizens in the development of the innovative strategies for promotion of cultural and natural heritage in your area?				
II. DETAILED EVALUATION	EXCELLENT VERY SATISFIED	GOOD SATISFIED	FAIR QUITE SATISFIED	INSUFFICIENT NOT SATISFIED
1. PRE-EVENT ORGANISATION				
Did you receive the invitation in good time?				
Did the invitation offer a clear picture of what the event was about?				
2. OBJECTIVES				
Selection of the objective(s)				
Did the event meet its objective(s)?				
How well did the event correspond to your expectations?				
3. HOW WOULD YOU RATE THE FOLLOWING?				
Quality of presentations - speakers				
Quality of co-creation sessions				

Documentation & Visual aid				
Quality of moderation and of the Hub team				
Structure and overall design of the event				
Level of interaction among participants				
Quality of the emerged co-created concepts				
4. LOGISTICAL ASPECTS				
On-site organisation and support				
Venue's facility (Hub)				
Did the venue offer an environment that supports creativity?				
5. COMMENTS				
1. What did you most appreciate during the event?				
2. Do you have any recommendation for the improvement of the organization of the next Hub activities?				

Thank you for your participation!

The RURITAGE project

Annex VIII – Draft event report

[Name of the organisation in charge of the event]

<i>Venue</i>	
<i>Date</i>	
<i>Duration</i>	
<i>Total number of participants</i>	
<i>Number of female participants</i>	
<i>Number of male participants</i>	
<i>Number of disable people, if applicable</i>	
<i>Number of migrants, if applicable</i>	

Agenda of the event

Please include the agenda of meeting.

Event assessment

Overall how would you rate the success of this specific event?

- very successful
- fairly successful
- not too successful
- not successful at all

Please briefly describe the event including:

- used facilitation and co-creation techniques of CHMP (please indicate type and number). Ex: brainstorming, world café, role playing, storytelling, etc.
- main messages/lessons
- key results achieved specific comments made by members of the Hub

Max. one page

Please briefly describe main success and difficulties related to this specific event, if any. Please provide suggestions for similar or future events (including improvement you would like to apply in the next events you will organize).

Max. half page

Annex IX - Project Information Sheet

RURITAGE Information Sheet

[NOTE: This is a template to inform participants about the RURITAGE project. It may be adapted according to each partner's communication needs and can be provided in the form of information sheet, covering letter or leaflet. It should be printed on the partner headed paper, (where appropriate) or in any case bear the partner's logo with full contact details. Please consider that it should normally contain at least the following information]

What is RURITAGE?

The RURITAGE project is **funded by the European Commission** within the H2020 programme and it will last for 4 years from June 2018 till May 2022. RURITAGE is led by the University of Bologna and counts 38 partners coming from 14 EU countries, Iceland, Norway, Turkey and 1 South American country (Colombia). The partners represent a very diverse range of actors encompassing local and regional authorities, universities and research centres, international networks and organizations, non-profit associations, and innovation centres.

RURITAGE aims at establishing a **new rural regeneration paradigm** able to turn **rural areas in sustainable development demonstration laboratories**, through the **enhancement** of their unique **Cultural and Natural Heritage potential**.

To do so, RURITAGE has identified **6 Systemic Innovation Areas** (pilgrimages; sustainable local food production; migration; art and festivals; resilience; and integrated landscape management) which showcase **heritage potential** as a **powerful engine** for **economic, social and environmental development of rural areas**.

The project has selected 13 **Role Models**, as **good practices to be analysed and studied**, to **replicate** those in **6 Replicators case study** selected within the project. Those 6 case studies will have to **develop** their **heritage-led regeneration strategies** based on the 6 SIAs mentioned above.

To do so each Role Model and Replicator will establish a **Local Rural Heritage Hubs** (RHH) as the main innovation place of the case studies involved, **gathering stakeholders and civil society**. Within Replicators, Rural Heritage Hubs will work as **living labs** where heritage-led rural regeneration **strategies** will be **co-created and implemented**, while in Role Models they will reinforce the ownership of cultural and natural heritage.

Would you like to be part of RURITAGE?

We would like to invite you to take part in the [NAME OF THE CASE STUDY] Rural Heritage Hub. Your role is crucial since you will be supporting us in the definition of the strategies and the particular actions to be promoted in our territory. Moreover, you will be part of a local community of stakeholders that aim at finding sustainable ways to regenerate our territory.

Before you decide whether or not to take part, it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. So, please take a bit of your time to read the following information carefully.

First of all if something is not clear, please don't hesitate to ask explanations to [NAME OF THE RHH COORDINATOR] from [NAME OF THE ORGANIZATION]. He/she will be pleased to support you. RURITAGE aims at involving various participants in the local Rural Heritage Hub in the process of understanding, defining, implementing and monitoring heritage-led regeneration strategies that will be put in place in [NAME OF THE CASE STUDY].

You have been invited to this study because RURITAGE aims at involving very different stakeholders to get an inclusive and shared strategy to be implemented.

What does it mean for you?

If you wish to participate in our Rural Heritage Hub you will be invited to attend meetings, workshops, public events or focus groups that will be implemented in our territory from now and for the following months. Most of the activities will be implemented in Spring 2019, and the overall process will last until May 2022.

Your participation is absolutely voluntary and you can decide to withdraw from the project at any moment you would like to, without any consequence at all.

Which are the expected project results and participants' benefits?

Major impact will be obtained by co-developing tailored regeneration strategies to preserve and promote the cultural and natural heritage of the rural territory you live in.

The project will establish 19 Rural Heritage Hubs in different countries of Europe and beyond. Around 400 people will be involved in those Hubs to co-develop with the project partners and Hub facilitators tailored heritage-led regeneration actions and measure to support the sense of ownership of cultural and natural heritage in rural areas.

With your participation you will also make a substantial contribution in promoting a sense of ownership of cultural and natural heritage of rural areas across Europe and empowering individuals across large sections of society to take a greater responsibility for their own territories, traditions and cultures.

After the end of the study you can contact the Hub Coordinator and ask them to provide you with the overall outcomes resulting from the research activities, in case you are interest in having further details on project results.

Your privacy is important to us!

Your personal data will be processed by [NOTE: insert name of partner who will collect the data] only for the purposes of the RURITAGE project and will not be disclosed to any external sources, except for project partners and technology and service providers, where needed. Video-recordings and photographs taken during meetings, photo sessions and interviews will be published on the RURITAGE and the partners’ web sites, only if you have expressly agreed.

Data will be used in accordance with the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and [NOTE: INSERT NATIONAL LEGISLATION OF THE PARTNER IN CHARGE OF COLLECTING DATA], both available at [INSERT LINK]

You have the right to request access, modification and cancellation of your data, as foreseen by the GDPR.

Full data protection information is available here [INSERT LINK] and will be handed to you with a leaflet you may consult at any time.

You will be able to request modification or removal of your data at any time by writing at (**INDICATE E-MAIL**).

For any further information, please refer to **NAME AND E-MAIL**

Date and place

CONSENT FOR THE VOLUNTARY PARTICIPATION IN THE PROJECT

I confirm that I have read and understood the RURITAGE information sheet dated (version XX) concerning my involvement in the RURITAGE project. I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have had these answered satisfactorily.	<input type="checkbox"/>
I understand that my participation is absolutely voluntary and that I am totally free to withdraw at any time without giving any reason.	<input type="checkbox"/>
I agree to take part in the RURITAGE project.	<input type="checkbox"/>

I declare that I have read and understood the information on data protection and that I have been able to solve any doubts with the help of the RURITAGE team, who has provided all the explanations I have requested.	<input type="checkbox"/>
I give my consent to the processing of my personal data as explained in the privacy information, in relation to my involvement in the RURITAGE project.	<input type="checkbox"/>
I agree in particular that my image and voice be recorded in the RURITAGE project videos (e.g. at meetings, workshops, interviews, etc.) and that such videos be published on the project's and on the partners' websites.	<input type="checkbox"/>

Name

.....

Date

.....

Signature

.....